

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 512

DATE: 23/11/97

Take off: 1050

Landing: 1810

Aircraft Scientist : A. KAYE
Flight Leader : T. RILEY
Others PSAP : M. RILEY
BAG FILMING : D. SIMLEY
D. TIDDEMAN
SPIN : D. FOWLER
G. WILSON

Captain : C. O'BRIEN
Co-pilot : L. PUNCE
Navigator : J. CANNING
Engineer : K. QUICK
Loadmaster : K. CROSS

Trials Instructions WILFI: MIRC : METHANE FLUXES
Operating area : ROND UK

General synoptic situation

TIME :

Start time	End time	Event	Height	Hdg	Comments
110708	111344	P1.1	6000' -500'	180	
111749	111904	P1.2	500' -50'	085	
112009	112038	P2.1	100' -500'		
112142	112211	P2.2	500' -1000'		
112329	112351	P2.3	1000' -1500'		
112527	112633	P3.1	1500' -700'		
112657	113535	R1	700'	090	
113954	120322	R2	700'	058	
120400	121820	R3	700'	050	
121843	123932	R4	700' -2000'	030	
124215	124258	P4.1	50' -100'		
124400	124431	P4.2	100-500'		
124551	124625	P4.3	500' -1000'		
124739	124803	P4.4	1000' -1500'		
124948	125442	P4.5	1500' -FL60		
125442	130155	R5	FL60	330	
130155	130729	P5	FL60-1000'	330	
130729	132138	R6	1000'	330	
132942	133004	P6.1	50' -100'	355	
133118	133148	P6.2	100' -500'		
133242	133303	P6.3	500' -1000'		
133419	133444	P6.4	1000' -1500'		
133752	134218	P6.5	1500' -6000'	395	
135154	140457	R7	100'	350	
140724	140745	P7.1	50' -100'		
141048	141140	P7.2	100' -500'		
141301	141353	P7.3	500' -1000'		
141511	141603	P7.4	1000' -1500'		
141937	142538	R8	100'	280	
142856	143852	R9	FL60	275	
145811	150727	R10	FL60	270	
150846	151416	P8.1	FL60-1500'	145	
151534	151608	P8.2	1500' -1000'		
151723	151757	P8.3	1000' -500'		
151903	151947	P8.4	500' -100'		
152106	154514	R11	100'	155	
155347	155426	P9.1	50' -100'		
155525	155600	P9.2	100' -500'		
155703	155735	P9.3	500' -1000'		
155846	155923	P9.4	1000' -1500'		
160649	160621	P9.5	1500' -FL60		
160621	160749	R12	FL60	180	
161210	172728	R13	100'		
172728	172820	P10.1	100' -500'		
173538	173607	P10.2	500' 1000'		
173715	173742	P10.3	1000' -1500'		
173917	174417	P10.4	1500' -FL60		

Land at Lyneham

Take off from Lyneham

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log ✓ Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log
	✓ Flight Leader pre-flight check form ✓ Flight Leader in-flight check form ✓ Flight Leader in-flight log ✓ Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
	SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEIMOS log Chemistry log
	Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)
	Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track

28/01/97

UK Trace Gas Flux Measurements

Sortie Objective:

To measure the flux of methane, carbon dioxide and nitrous oxide from the UK.

Location: United Kingdom coastal waters.

Weather: Anticyclonic, airflow must be such that air crossing the UK is not contaminated with pollutants from Eastern Europe, *i.e.* airflow ideally from West to East but air flow from North East to South west accepted.

Flight Pattern:

[1] Depart Lyneham/Boscombe Down and transit to initial way point Q
[2] Execute stepped profile from minimum safe altitude to the top of the boundary layer at 1000feet/min. Profile to be interrupted for short runs approx. 30 seconds) at levels to be decided.

(a) _____, (b) _____, (c) _____, (d) _____, (e) _____

[3] Return to 500 feet for straight and level bag filling run. Remain at this level for 60-70 nm.

[4] Repeat [2] and [3] until between way points V and K.

[5] Cross UK to way point G, continue sampling pattern.

[6] Return to Lyneham *via* way point Q.

Intensive sampling periods at 180 kts otherwise 190/5 kts.

SF26: Prof David Fowler (Institute of terrestrial Ecology - Edinburgh) and Dr Geraint Morgan (Open University)

ATTENTION - ANDREW KAYE

Set-out below is an update of the "tiger" waypoints in case we need them next week. If you are considering a night-stop in Leuchars or Turnhouse we will need to know early for clearance purposes.

For your consideration, Leuchars - via south coast - Leuchars takes approx 8hrs (still air) and Leuchars - via north coast - Leuchars takes approx 4hrs (still air). Transit to/from Leuchars will take approx 1hr 45mins.

If you wish to identify the points with letters (as per your brief) please let me know. My suggestion is as shown.

UPDATE OF "TIGER" WAYPOINTS

(* SIGNIFIES A CHANGE TO CO-ORDINATES)

(+ SIGNIFIES A NEW WAYPOINT)

				<u>Ident Letter</u>	
	T 1	N5026.0	W00501.7	ST MAWGAN TACAN	A
18	T 2	*N5119.0	W00530.0	BOUNDARY LFA2/LFA7	B
17	T 3	*N5210.6	W00530.0	BOUNDARY D201A	C
	T 4	*N5315.0	W00530.0	BOUNDARY D201B	D
16	T 4A	*N5326.2	W00530.0	BOUNDARY LFA7/LFA17	D1
15	T 5	*N5431.0	W00509.0	BOUNDARY LFA17/LFA16	E
14	T 5A	+N5507.7	W00546.0	BOUNDARY LFA16/LFA14	E1
13	T 6	N5545.0	W00640.0		F
12	T 7	N5650.0	W00720.0 5650.0N 0500.0W		G
	T 8	N5745.0	W00635.0		H
	T 9	N5910.0	W00500.0		I
	T 9A	+N5930.0	W00300.0		I1
	T10	*N5925.0	W00136.0		J
	T11	*N5750.0	W00156.0		K
	T11A	*N5730.0	W00130.0		K1
11	T11B	*N5700.0	W00130.0		K2
10	T11C	N5600.0	E00030.0	BOUNDARY LFA14/LFA12	K3
9	T12	N5500.0	E00130.0	BOUNDARY LFA12/LFA11	L
8	T13	*N5353.0	E00107.0		M
7	T13A	+N5309.0	E00146.0	BOUNDARY LFA11/LFA5	M1
6	T14	*N5230.0	E00220.0	02430.0 0144.0	N
5	T15	*N5130.0	E00152.0 5110N	BOUNDARY LFA5/LFA18	O
4	T16	N5040.0	E00100.0		P
3	T17	*N5000.0	W00032.0	BOUNDARY D059	Q
	T17A	+N5040.0	W00100.0	(ALTERNATE TO T17 - IF REQUIRED)	Q1
	T18	+N5000.0	W00142.2	BOUNDARY D049	R
2	T18A	*N5000.0	W00200.0	BOUNDARY LFA18/LFA2	R1
22	T19	*N5001.0	W00300.0		S
21	T19A	+N4947.0	W00317.0	BOUNDARY D004	S1
20	T20	*N4928.0	W00500.0	BOUNDARY D008A	T
19	T21	N5000.0	W00600.0		U

~~TO HAWAII ACHED 01252 376588~~

~~HAWAII, THIS IS OUR IMPROVED FLIGHT PLAN - DO YOU GLOSSER ANY PROBLEMS?~~

~~KEN~~

Flight Plan - 28 January 1997

Transit to south coast as convenient, descend to 500 ft (or lower) ASL straight and level. Maintain 500 ft altitude between profile ascents. Transit across Scotland at minimum safe altitude.

A512

GPS data
07:31:53 - 18:16:26

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye

Project: TOWER Date: 28/1/97
 Flight No: A512 Page 1 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
11:00:22 TRANSIT.		TRANS	600 P		190	51.00	-1.86	EGDL T/O 10:42:03 7/8 sc below broken ahead clear over sea and overhead.	
11:07:08		P1	600 P		171	50.51	-1.89	6/8 Broken cu below clear above. ^{wides of} Stroudland bay. →	
11:12:00		P1	700 P		192	50.26	-1.99	clear above & below, but cloudy ahead.	
11:13:40		P1.1	500 R		192	50.17	-2.04	interupt profile at 500' because of cloud ahead.	
11:17:49		P1.2	500 R		81	50.01	-2.04	hazy with 3/8 cu above	
11:19:04		P1.2	50 R		84	50.02	-1.92	'	
								Filled bags at 100, 500, 1000, 3000 ft.	
								in cloud layer at 1500 ft.	
11:26:57		R1	700 R		85	50.01	-1.30	Hazy and overcast.	
11:32:42			700 R		88	50.01	-1.00	Hazy and overcast.	
11:38:00								end of run.	
11:39:54		R2	700 R		57	50.02	-50	7/8 cu above and hazy - 11:45:20 Bag filling	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye

Project: TIAER Date: 28/1/17
 Flight No: A512 Page 2 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
11:57:06		R2	700		58			hazy and cloudy above.	
12:02:11		R2	700	R	49	50.61	0.87	clear above hazy with sc ahead. sea	
12:03:22		R3e	700	R	45	50.65	0.94	Sea surface is clearer.	
12:04:00		R3	700	R	46	50.68	0.97	3 inch mark on video film video of A/E shadow on water.	
12:11:28		R3	700	R	43	50.92	1.36	Sc above, blue sky visible around. French EUK shores and lots of ship traffic.	
12:16:16		R3	700	R	37	51.11	1.61	clear above but very hazy... Perry & cat @ 5-7 min	
12:17:20		R3	700	R	36	51.18	1.69	Hazy some wisps of c below building ahead	
12:18:48		R4	700	R	28	51.20	1.71	clear above. ozone increase at m & then level.	
12:21:45								Solid cloud below request made to drop below cloud.	
								12:24:09 Dropping below cloud.	
								12:27:01 below cloud at 300. 1042 <u>SS3</u>	
12:32:47						51.79	2.16	climbing to 1200ft to get clear of cloud.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye.

Project: TIGER Date: 28/1/97
Flight No: A512 Page 3 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
						12:39:26			
12:42:15		P4.1	50	R	22	52.25	2.50	broken cu haze Bag fills @ 100 500 1000 1500 6000ft.	
12:49:48		P4.3	1500	R	327	52.56	2.63	hazy but cloud free above and below.	
12:54:44		R5	FL60	P	328	52.76	2.42	Some ci visible ahead but otherwise <u>no cloud</u>	
13:01:55		P5	FL60	P	327	53.10	2.00	Oil rig clearly visible - clear.	
13:07:38		R6	1000	R	326	53.33	1.73	<u>Haze layer @ 2500 Rad.</u> Good vis. 1036 Regional 355	
13:21:38		R6e	1000	R	335	53.89	0.99	good vis no cloud but haze ahead.	
13:29:44		P6	50	R	352	54.27	0.89	Some sc ahead but clear cloud free above. 1043 sesfalet4	
13:42:18		P6e	1000	R	346	54.47	0.69	100, 500, 1000, 1500 samples. - 3/8 sc below clear above	
13:45:01		P7						1500 → soft bag fills and vert structure extra profile. may not be in flight leaders logs.	
13:51:25		P7						end of profile.	
13:52:00		R7	160	R	345	55.30	0.49	clear 1042 <u>SS 4</u>	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kaye*

Project: *TIGER* Date: *28/1/97*
 Flight No: *A512* Page 4 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
14:02:24		R7	100	R	343	55.93	0.19	clear, some sc on the horizon ahead.	
14:04:59		R7e	100	R	359	55.91	0.16	high level cloud to south and east.	
14:07:54		P7.1	50	R	271	55.90	-0.04	Broken SC ahead Sun shining, 1042 Sea state 4-5	
								100, 500, 1000 & 1500 values.	
								DROP BACK to 100 ft	
14:19:37		R8	100	R	275	55.91	-1.09	patches of SC above clear.	
14:25:38		R8c	100	R	277	55.93	-1.57	Clear some patches of SC above and ahead. Run cut short to enable 10 mins @ FL60 FL60	
14:28:57		R9	60	FL	270	55.94	-1.87	Clear above and below - hazy overland with some SC patches. Jet contrails available SW Ahead.	
14:38:34		R9e	60	FL	265	55.87	-2.88	good view of Edinburgh.	
14:58:11		R10	60	FL	266	55.67	-5.67	SC below clear above.	
15:07:27		R10	60	FL		55.66	-6.64	SC Below. <u>1040</u>	
15:08:46		P8.1	60	FL	137	55.69	+6.52	SC Below clear above.	
								Copilot. now alt 1040 Cloud top. 3400 EP "rain" water on windows 1500 just below cloud.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kays

Project: Tiger
Flight No: A512

Date: 28/7/97
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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
15:21:06		R11	100	R	147	55.16	18:25-1830 on ground	Small shower behind us. Cu ahead and patches of Sun.	
						-5.86		Bird strike.	
15:48:51		R11	1000					Under sheet of SC but broken cu ahead.	
15:53:48		P9.1	50	R	196	53.64		Sky ahead and broken cu but SC above visibility good.	
						-5.48		bag fill runs @ 100 500 1000 1500	
								Broke through cloud top ~ 3700	
16:06:22		P9e R12-200ft	60	FL	181	52.91 52.91		Sun shining into flight bright hazy layers of cloud ahead and below	
						-5.51			
16:12:10		R13	100ft	R	174	52.57		Clear with haze on horizon.	
						-5.53		1043 SS2.	
16:21:10		R13	100ft	R	178	52.11		passed just in front of Stena Ferry Fishguard to Roslar.	
						-5.52		clear hazy horizon, sun getting low in sky.	
16:26								Seastate 1 1042	
16:33:30								Bright edge of cloud above line to horizon port side clear south cloud north SS.3.	
16:43:24		R13	100ft	R	184			Having passed through the dirtiest Air today continuing 100ft until light fails. Broken cu above hazy horizon. occasional small white cap on sea.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kenye.

Project: FILER Date: 29/1/97
 Flight No: A512 Page 6 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
16:47:29		R13	100	R	184	50.74 -5.80	PSAP hit peak value. with ozone dropping.		
16:57:17		R13	100	R	187	50.25 -5.90	Light fading but horizon good broken in overhead lands end lighthouse		
17:05:37		R13	100	R	127	49.94 -5.73	visible 1/2 cu still good (1041 SS 4) light		
17:11:40		R13	100	R	123	49.77 -5.41	seas state 5		
17:18:07		R13	100	R	85	49.65 -5.04	in clean air Sc above.		
17:25:31		R13	100	R	87	49.66 -4.54	Sc above horizon still good.		
17:27:32		R13 P10.1	100	R	88	49.66 -4.37	Staying visual @ 550 ft. SC ABOVE and sea below. getting dark.		
							1000 1000 or 1500 samples plus 6000 out of the boundary layer.		
17:44:17		P10 and F160		P	19	49.93 -3.35	Completely dark no obs possible. out on clouds 3000.		
17:46:17		last Bag filled.					END END OF SCIENCE ALL BAGS FILLED!		

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A512 Date: 28/1/96 User: A. KAYE
Interactive by: I. RUE
Date: 30/1/97

Renav

KALMAN FILTERING - APPLIED

TWC

Profile plotted: No — NO DEEP PROFILES CARRIED OUT IN FLIGHT
Line chosen: Profile / Whole flight / Other

a = -0.5499 E+1
b = +0.3083 E-2
c = +0.5241 E-6

LWC

OK

Heimann / Barnes

NOT USED

ICTP — RECALIBRATED

FWVS — NOT CONNECTED DUE TO LACK OF ASILFWVS_DIAGS.DAT IN INTDATA:

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: 4512

Date: 28/1/97

A/S Name: A. KAYE

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for 3, OPEN UN1, U.F. LRF.....
2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period
3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project
4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long? 10 yrs.....
5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO GAVE TAPE TO A. KAYE
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?
6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in?
7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: AS12 Date: 28/1/17

Page...of 2

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
<u>0756</u>	REF +	5	<u>0566</u>	✓			
	REF -	7	<u>2854</u>	✓			Approx 0568
	AOSS	19	<u>6095</u>		F/S TORQUE <u>4.5</u>		Approx 2858
	AOA	18	<u>6095</u>		O/S TORQUE <u>3.5</u>		2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	<u>0000</u>				2047 st. and level
	PR HT	8	<u>3060</u>	<u>-200</u>	✓		As Indicated 0000
	CABP	14	<u>3303</u>	<u>1020</u>	✓		As Altimeter
	A/S	9	<u>0000</u>	✓			As ASI 0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	<u>0161</u>				
	UP2S	82	<u>0150</u>				
	UIRS	83	<u>2018</u>				
	UP1Z	84	<u>0150</u>	✓			Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	<u>0144</u>	✓			Approx 0149
	UIRZ	86	<u>2032</u>	✓			Approx 2061
	UP1T	87	<u>2777</u>				As IAT
	UP2T	88	<u>2874</u>				As IAT
	UIRT	89	<u>2831</u>				As IAT
	LP1S	91	<u>0102</u>				
	LP2S	92	<u>4095</u>				
	LIRS	93	<u>4095</u>				
	LP1Z	94	<u>4095</u>				Approx 0150
	LP2Z	95	<u>4095</u>				Approx 0146
	LIRZ	96	<u>4095</u>				Approx 2050
	LP1T	97	<u>4095</u>				As IAT
	LP2T	98	<u>4095</u>				As IAT
	LIRT	99	<u>4095</u>				As IAT
	J/W	42	<u>0997</u>	✓	<u>0.0</u>		As Indicated 0000
	NEPH	47					
	HYGR	58	<u>2472</u>	<u>0</u>			
	HYCC	59	<u>0693</u>	✓			696-901
	FDEW	138	<u>1992</u>	<u>0</u>			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	FSTA	139	<u>0608</u>				
	DTF	10	<u>0828</u>	<u>2</u>			
	DTC	11	<u>5</u>				
	NDTF	23	<u>2572</u>	<u>2</u>			same as De-Iced
	NDTC	24	<u>5</u>				
	INCT	48	<u>2671</u>	✓			
	CCN	140					less than 4095 if ON
	TWCD	70	<u>2183</u>				0000-4094
	TSAM	72	<u>0046</u>				0640-1860 < min
	O3	100	<u>3488</u>				
	O3P	106	<u>2604</u>				$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$
	O3RG	113	<u>0602</u>				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	0512	✓		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0880	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0750	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	11	✓		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
2030	1508 3854	2045	1024	2030	3744	2045	0127
	LATC	160	Dec	0000			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	0000			Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height:

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70	2164	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	0821	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	0048	✓		0840-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2123	?	low	2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2219	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2009	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2145	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1022	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4279			4095	
	EV1V	170	2045				
	EV2V	171	2045				
	NPWR	172	3553				
	EVIC	173	3067				
	EV2C	174	2067				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: AS12 Date: 28/1/97

Page...of 2

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1103	REF +	5	0567	✓			Approx 0568
	REF -	7	2853	✓			Approx 2858
	AOSS	19	1872	✓	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	1875	✓	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	4095	>5000	0000		As Indicated 0000
	PR HT	8	3123	0000	0000		As Altimeter
	CABP	14	3395	1031	1030		
	A/S	9	2169	200			As ASI 0000 - 0100
1225	UP1S	81	0906				
	UP2S	82	0657				
	UIRS	83	1868				
	UP1Z	84	0251	✓			Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	0147	✓			Approx 0149
	UIRZ	86	2041	✓			Approx 2061
	UP1T	87	2705				As IAT
	UP2T	88	2716				As IAT
	UIRT	89	2740				As IAT
	LP1S	91	0324				
	LP2S	92	0218				
	LIRS	93	1973				
	LP1Z	94	0148	✓			Approx 0150
	LP2Z	95	0162	✓			Approx 0148
	LIRZ	96	2057	✓			Approx 2050
	LP1T	97	2682				As IAT
	LP2T	98	2702				As IAT
	LIRT	99	2701				As IAT
	1449	J/W	42	1400	M.L		
NEPH		47					
HYGR		58	2502	1			
HYCC		59	0700	✓			696-901
FDEW		138	1999				DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
FSTA		139	0608	0			
DTF		10	2575	9			
DTC		11	5				
NDTF		23	2515	9			same as De-Iced
NDTC		24	5				
INCT		48	2666				
CCN		140					less than 4095 if ON
TWCD		70	2218				0000-4094
TSAM		72	1324				0640-1860 < min
O3	100	0141					
O3P	106	2580				$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
O3RG	113	1708					

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1620	FL NO	1	Hex	512			Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0162			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0122			Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0331			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
3171	1508	3172	0792	3172	3719	3171	0158
	3755						
	LATC	160	Dec	0592	S2N		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4033	S W		Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: 100

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70	2256			0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2518			2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1278			0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2725			2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2241			2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	1240			0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	1520			0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1014			0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095	✓		4095	
	EV1V	170	3473				
	EV2V	171	3158				
	NPWR	172	2683				
	EVIC	173	4019				
	EV2C	174	4004				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 512.....

Date 28/1/17.....

Page 1..... of 4.....

Video Tape	
No. ASIL #1	Ends 1356
(FFC) / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	51° 30.41N	51° 30.41N
Long	001° 59.16W	001° 59.17W
Time	0713	0714
Status	53 OK	GC ATU4V

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) / n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) / n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	(y) / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
07242			DATA ON						
08440			SIT INU TO NAV						
102403			T/O RAF LINGHAM						
105623			START VIDEO ASIL#1 COUNT = 0000						
			START P1.1 ↓						
110708	29	6000		180	140	0.5	-17	OFF	
			END / START PROFILE P1.1						
111344	30	500'	104	120					
			START P1.2 ↓						
111749	31	500'		085		4.9	2.4	OFF	
			END P1.2						
111904	32	50'	102						S=5
			START P2.1						
112004	34	100'							
			END P2.1						
112038	36	500'							
			START P2.2						
112142	38	500'							
			END P2.2						
112211	39	1000'							
			START P2.3						
112329	42	1000'							
			END P2.3						
112351	44	1500'							

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A S12 Date 28/1/97 Page 2 of 4

Video Tape
 No. A512#2
 Ends 1356
 FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	<u>52 49.95N</u>	<u>52 51.93N</u>
Long	<u>002 20.65E</u>	<u>002 17.58E</u>
Time	<u>1256</u>	<u>1257</u>
Status	<u>5's</u>	<u>NAV</u>

DRS recording to HORACE y/n
HORACE recording to disc y/n
SATCOM sending pos. reports y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
				START P 4.2					
<u>124400</u>	<u>126</u>	<u>100'</u>		<u>020</u>					
				END P 4.2					
<u>124431</u>	<u>128</u>	<u>500'</u>							
				START P 4.3					
<u>124551</u>	<u>131</u>	<u>500'</u>							
				END P 4.3					
<u>124625</u>	<u>132</u>	<u>1000'</u>							
				START P 4.4					
<u>124729</u>	<u>135</u>	<u>1000'</u>							
				END P 4.4					
<u>124803</u>	<u>136</u>	<u>1500'</u>							
				START P 4.5					
<u>124948</u>	<u>139</u>	<u>1500'</u>							
				END P 4.5					
<u>125442</u>	<u>141</u>	<u>FL6000'</u>	<u>1013</u>	<u>330</u>	<u>190</u>	<u>3</u>	<u>-12</u>	<u>OFF</u>	
				END RUN 5					
<u>130155</u>	<u>147</u>	<u>FL60</u>	<u>1013</u>	<u>330</u>	<u>190</u>				
				END RUN 5 / START P 5					
<u>130729</u>	<u>148</u>	<u>1000'</u>	<u>1086</u>	<u>330</u>	<u>195</u>	<u>5</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>OFF</u>	<u>360/16</u> <u>SS=3</u>
				END RUN 6					
<u>132138</u>	<u>164</u>	<u>1000'</u>	<u>1036</u>	<u>330</u>	<u>198</u>	<u>5</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>OFF</u>	
				START PROFILE P 6.17					
<u>132942</u>	<u>170</u>	<u>500'</u>	<u>1042</u>	<u>355</u>	<u>170</u>				<u>SS=4</u>
				END P 6.1					
<u>133004</u>	<u>172</u>	<u>100'</u>							

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A S12.....

Date 28/1/97.....

Page 3 of 4.....

Video Tape	
No.	AS12 #2
Ends	1654
☒ FFC / ☐ DFC / ☐ RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	55 54.07N	55 52.60N
Long	007 46.48W	007 57.51W
Time	1429	1430
Status	5 1/2	MAV

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ y / ☐ n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ y / ☐ n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	☒ y / ☐ n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
		500'		END P 7.2					
141140	220	500'		#					
				START P 7.3					
141301	223	500'							
				END P 7.3					
141353	225	1000'							
				START P 7.4					
141511	227	1000'							
				END P 7.4					
141603	228	1500'							
		4000'		START P 7.5					
				START RUN 8					
141937	231	100'	1042	280	190	7	4	OFF	SS=4
				END RUN 8					
142555	240	100'	1042	280	190	7.2	3.4	OFF	
	↑								
				START RUN 9					
142856	241	FL60		275	185	3	-4	OFF	
				END RUN 9					
143852	251	FL60		270	182	3.9	-4.1	OFF	
				START RUN 10					
145811	252	FL60	1042	270		3.9	-5	OFF	
				END RUN 10					
150727	261	FL60							

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No **A 512**.....

Date **28/1/97**.....

Page **4** of **4**.....

Video Tape
No. AS12#2
Ends 1654
(FFC) / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	51 52.61N	51 50.00 N
Long	005 30.81W	005 31.7W
Time	1025	1026
Status	5's	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE (y) / n
HORACE recording to disc (y) / n
SATCOM sending pos. reports (y) / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
				START	P	9.4			
155846	310	1000'		END	P	9.4			
155923	311	1500'		START	P	9.5			
160049	314	1500'		END	P	9.5 / START	RUN	12	
160021	315	FL600	1013	185	195	1	-6	OFF	
				END	RUN	12			
160749	318	FL600	1013	190	185	1	-6	OFF	
				START	RUN	13			
161210	319	1000'	1043	180	190	7	4	OFF	SS=2
				END					
			1043						SS= 2 3
164935	383	END	VIDEO	TAPE	A 512#2	CARD =	597	7	
165019	380	START	VIDEO	TAPE	A 512#3	CARD =	0000		
1705			1041						SS=4
1711				START					SS=5
1719				START					075/10 kt
				END	RUN	13 / START	P	10.1	
172725	426	1000'		END	P	10.1			
172820	427	500'		START	P	10.2			
173538	435	500'							

Video Tape	
No.	AS12#1
Ends	1356
☒ FFC / ☐ DFC / ☐ RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	50 00.16N	49 59.85N
Long	001 12.55W	001 08.66W
Time	1129	1150
Status	5's	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ / n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ / n
SATCOM sending pos reports	☒ / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/Sea st.
						3.1			
11227	46	1500'							
						3.1			
112637	45	700'							
112657	50	700'							
113535	60	700'							
113954	63	700'							
120322	85	700'							
120400	86	700'							
121720	104	700'							
121843	106	700	1042						
123932	120	2000'	1042						SS=3
124215	121	50'							
124258	122	100'	1042						SS=2

Video Tape	
No. AS12#2	
Ends 1654	
(FFC) / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	SS 39.35N	SS 41.25N
Long	000 20.53E	000 18.35E
Time	1400	1401
Status	S3	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) / n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) / n
SATCOM sending pos reports	(y) / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			START P6.2						
133118	174	100'							
			END P6.2						
133148	176	500'							
			START P6.3						
133242	178	500'							
			END P6.3						
133303	179	1000'							
			START P6.4						
133419	182	1000'							
			END P6.4						
133444	183	1500'							
			START P6.5						
133752	186	1500'							
			END P6.5						
134218	187	6000'	1042	395					
			START RUN 7						
135154	198	100'	1042	350	190	7.5	4.1	OFF	SS=3/4
135335	201		END VIDEO A 512#1						COUNT = 6043
135428	203		START VIDEO AS12#2						COUNT = 0000
135520			HANNANN CAL Prog 6				10 → 0		
			END RUN 7						
140457	211	100'	1042	350	110				
			START P 7.1						
140724	213	50'	1042						SS=4/5
			END P7.1						
140745	215	100'							
			START P 7.2						
141048	219	100'							

Video Tape

No. AS12#2
 Ends 1654
 (FFC) / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	54 26.71N	54 24.16N
Long	005 08.71W	005 09.95W
Time	1537	1537
Status	5's	KAV

DRS recording to HORACE (y) / n

HORACE recording to disc (y) / n

SATCOM sending pos reports (y) / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
				START PROFILE 8.1					
150846	262	FLOOR		145	180				
				END PROFILE 8.1					
151416	263	1500'		165					
				START PROFILE 8.2					
151534	266	1500'							
				END P8.2					
151608	268	1000'							
				START P8.3					
151723	271	1000'							
				END P8.3					
151757	272	500'							
				START P8.4					
151903	275	500'							
				END P8.4					
151947	276	100'							
				START P8.5 RUN 11					
152100	279	100'	1045	155	180	8	4	OFF	SS=2
				END P8.5					
				END RUN 11					
154514	296	100'							SS=1
				START P 9.1					
155347	299	50'	1045						SS=2
				END P9.1					
155426	300	100'							
				START P 9.2					
155525	302	100'							
				END P9.2					
155600	304	500'							
				START P 9.3					
155703	306	500'							
				END P9.3					
155735	307	1000'							

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

FLIGHT NO: A512

DATE: 28/1/197

MRF 1

INSTRUMENT	FITTED	OPERATED	COMMENTS
NAVIGATION: GPS OMEGA INU RADALT	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	 ✓	
THERMOMETERS: DI TEMP NDI TEMP ICTP HEIMANN HYGROMETERS: GEN. EASTERN TWC FWVS J/W EXP. PITOT HEAD: STATIC PRESS. PITOT PRESS. GUST VANES	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	 ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	
RADIOMETERS: UPPER CLEAR UPPER RED UPPER SILICON LOWER CLEAR LOWER RED LOWER SILICON MARSS SAFIRE DEIMOS ARIES	 ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	 ✓ X X X	
CHEMISTRY: OZONE ECGC NOX	✓ X X	✓ ✓	
OTHERS: CCN CLOUD PHYSICS CABIN PRESS NEPHELOMETER PSAP	✓ ✓ ✓ X ✓	X X ✓	

- ① HOSS TECHNIQUE A-D-HIGHT @ 4:5
- ② USUAL LOWER BDR PROBLEM PRE-FLIGHT / AND AFTER T/O
- ③ HORACE CALCULATED WINDS / WIND SPEED QUITE WRONG COMPARED TO NAVS WINDS — INU SEEMS OK, VANDS SEEM OK. OTHER STANDARDS PAULA'S SEEM OK
- ④ PRE-FLIGHTING DATA NEEDS TO BE RECHECKED WITH T/WRAP'S.

GET 4 POSITIONS FOR THE VAN DOORS — DO NOT SLAM

From: XV208 28/01/97 1234Z
 To: Aircraft Manager
 Hi

We are having some problems with cloud. Can you check the latest satpic and let us know the location of low cloud in the north sea.

Cheers

Ian

1200 Vis All low level (mostly Sc) cloud

Up to $S2\frac{1}{2}^{\circ}N$, $E \rightarrow W$. Thin cloud

Then virtually clear slot ~~cloud~~

near E coast up to $S7^{\circ}N$, $2\frac{1}{2}^{\circ}W$

~~to~~

Broken cloud on W. Scottish coast
 $S6^{\circ}N \downarrow S4^{\circ}N$, $S-6^{\circ}W$

Mostly clear Irish Sea
 $\downarrow S2^{\circ}N S^{\circ}W$ then cloud.

Cloud SW peninsula.
 until approx Plymouth

then mostly clear $fee \rightarrow$ Tow.

Flight Plan - 28 January 1997

Transit to south coast as convenient, descend to 500 ft (or lower) ASL straight and level. Maintain 500 ft altitude between profile ascents. ~~Transit across Scotland at minimum safe altitude.~~

○ = approximate start position of PSAP filter exposure.

P.S.A.P Log

Flight No. ...A512.....

Date ...28.1.97.....

Project ...ROADS BRITAIN.....

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ Start of Run	Height	Run	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ End of Run	Remarks
Set to DRS 0917 time ✓	New filter Tr = 1.000	Set to 2.5 lpm	21.7	Levels 35 156	Ave = 30 s	FILTER	← Preflight ONLY
105420	0.847	2.45	0.8	FL60		①	Switch on, same filter in (P1)
111039	0.847	2.4	2.1	FL30	P1 ↓	①	On profile down.
1118							End Profile. Change filter (P2)
112443	0.995	2.62	2.2	1500ft	P2.	②	First stepped profile up.
113105	0.990	2.45	3.0	1000ft	R1	②	In Run 1
113536	0.987	2.45	1.6	1000ft	R2	②	Start Run 2
113954	0.986	2.46	1.2	700ft	R3	②	End Run 2 / Start R3
115210	0.981	2.45	2.7	700ft	R2	②	
120304	0.974	2.44	1.5	700ft	R3	②	End Run 2 / Start Run 3
121740	0.970	2.44	0.7	700ft	R3	②	Near end of Run 3.
122413	0.968	2.43	1.6	descending	R4	②	Descend to try + clear cloud. - too low
123232	0.965	2.50	1.6	climbing 1000ft	R4	②	Level at 1200ft to avoid cloud.

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ Start of Run	Height	Run	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ End of Run	Remarks
123950	0.964	2.5	0.1	700ft	4	FILTER ②	End Run 4.
124305	0.961	2.57	5.8	100ft	P4.1	②	More soot at this level.
124522	0.958	2.54	7.2	500ft	P4.2	②	Higher
124705	0.956	2.50	0.5	1000ft	P4.3	②	Soot dropped off at this height
124835	0.956	2.45	0.0	1500ft	P4.4	②	Back to clean air
125440	0.957	2.48	0.0	6000ft	R5	②/③	Change filter, / Start Run
② 130136	1.000	2.47	0.0	6000ft	R5	③/④	End Run / change filter
130738	0.992	2.96	1.5	100ft	R6	④	start , start Run 6
132156	0.989	2.53	0.8	1000ft	R6	④	End Run
132911	0.988	2.56	1.8	300ft		④	Descending
133004	0.988	2.52	3.5	100ft	R6 P6.1	④	In the run N. of Humber est.
133206	0.987	2.49	0.9	500ft	P6.2	④	Lower soot amounts than previous profiles
133335	0.986	2.45	0.8	1000ft	P6.3	④	
133409	0.986	2.45	1.6	1000ft	R6	④	
133540	0.985	2.42	0.7	1500ft	P6.4	④	
133805	0.985	2.40	0.3	1500ft	P6.5	④	Climb up to 6000ft.
134835	0.985	2.55	0.1	1000ft	R6	④	Profile down
135005	0.984	2.56	1.9	500ft	?	④	
135220	0.983	2.51	1.7	100ft	R7	④	Not Not as much as S-Coast.

P.S.A.P Log

Flight No. ...A512.....

Date28-1-97.....

Project ...ROUND BRITAIN.....

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ Start of Run	Height	Run	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ End of Run	Remarks
Set to DRS time	New filter Tr = 1.000	Set to 2.5 lpm		Levels 1	Ave = s	End of Run FILTER	← Preflight ONLY
140302	0.977	2.52	1.1	100ft	R7	④	Fairly low counts.
140805	0.976	2.51	1.4	100ft	P7.1	④ ④	Counts again lower than before
141105	0.975	2.49	2.2	500ft	P7.2	④	Hdy twds Abbr head.
141435	0.973	2.46	0.2	1000'	P7.3	④	Above inversion
141745	0.974	2.41	0.1	1500'	P7.4	④	Clean.
142035	0.970	2.50	10.5	100'	R8	④	Counts comparable w/ S. coast lvs
142340	0.964	2.50	7.2	100'	R8	④	Last run on E. coast
142540	0.961	2.51	7.0	100'	R8	④	End Run, climb to FL60
143030	1.00	1.53	0.0	FL60	R9	⑤	Change filter. Over land run
143836	0.999	2.52	0.0	FL60	R9	⑤	End Run.
145835	0.999	2.4	0.7	FL60	R10	⑤	Shut down, crossing W. coast.
150715	1.000	2.50	0.0	FL60	R10	⑤ / ⑥	End run, change filter

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ Start of Run	^{40/56} Height	Run	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ End of Run FILTER	Remarks
151105	1.000	2.56	0.00	FL60	P8.1x	⑥	Ready for Profile down
151240	0.999	2.49	7.0	3000ft	P8.1	⑥	Starting to see some particles
151508	0.999	2.48	0.0	1500ft		⑥	Clean!
151640	0.999	2.51	1.0	1000ft	P8.2	⑥	"
151835	0.998	2.56	1.0	500ft	P8.3	⑥	"
152020	0.998	2.58	0.4	100ft	P8.4	⑥	"
153618	0.998	2.52	0.0	100ft	R11	⑥	"
154518	0.995	2.50	1.7	100ft	R11	⑥	End run.
155256	0.989	2.51	0.0	300ft	—	⑥/⑦	Change filter
155530	1.000	2.45	0.2	800ft	P9.2	⑦	Clean
155633	1.000	2.42	0.0	500ft	P9.3	⑦	"
155805	0.999	2.45	0.6	1000ft	P9.3	⑦	"
160020	0.999	2.43	0.0	1500ft	P9.4	⑦	"
161235	0.997	2.47	4.3	100ft	R13	⑦	Box into the polluted air now.
162045	0.983	2.47	4.5	100ft	R13	⑦	Abeam S. Wales
162639	0.973	2.47	10.1	100ft	R13	⑦	Getting muckier, longer land crossings
163333	0.953	2.46	8.7	100ft	R13	⑦	counts falling back now.
164305	0.934	2.47	10.8	100ft	R13	⑦	
164728	0.924	2.45	15.8	100ft	R13	⑦	

P.S.A.P Log

Flight No.A512.....

Date28.1.97.....

Project ..Round Britain.....

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ Start of Run	Height	Run	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ End of Run	Remarks
Set to DRS time	New filter Tr = 1.000	Set to 2.5 lpm		Levels 1	Ave = s		← Preflight ONLY
165116	0.913	2.45	12.2	100ft	R13	⑦ / ⑧	change filter before hands out
165433	0.999	2.46	9.0	100ft	R13	⑧	/ back into clean air ↓
170108	0.992	2.54	2.0	100ft	R13	⑧	almost at hands out. ≈ 1 mi
170540	0.990	2.54	1.5	100ft	R13	⑧	running along south coast.
171251	0.988	2.49	1.4	100ft	R13	⑧	
172145	0.982	2.50	3.0	100ft	R13	⑧	beyond the Lizard, still fairly clean
172737	0.976	2.51	3.6	100ft	R13	⑧	End Run
172905	0.976	2.48	2.0	550'	R13 P10.1	⑧	stopped profile, getting dark.
173311	0.974	2.47	1.9	550'	P10.	⑧	stay at 101 till past dergo over.
173633	0.972	2.49	1.1	1000ft	P10.2	⑧	Clear.
173835	0.971	2.47	1.6	1500'	P10.3	⑧	clear.
174422	0.972	2.34	2.3	FL60	P10.4	⑧ / ⑨	climb to F60, change filter.

A512 28-JAN-97 16:31:45 349 Ω 51.56 -5.61 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
185.	1037.	-0.6	168.	7.1	4.6	032/11

OZONE MR 18.17 PSAP LIN 1.45
ppb E-5m-1

2.50
2.00
1.50
1.00
0.50
0.00

A B C D E F G H
SELECT PARAS FREQ ZOOM VIDEO HELP

A512 28-JAN-97 17:46:15 446 Ω 50.02 -3.35 RV P

HDG degT 16.	SPR mb 812.	PHGT kft 6.0	TAS knots 199.	TAT C 1.1	DEW C -10.5	WIND deg m/s 128/12
--------------------	-------------------	--------------------	----------------------	-----------------	-------------------	---------------------------

OZONE MR 47.60 PSEP LIN 5.00
ppb E-S m-1

A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
-------------	------------	-----------	-----------	---	---	------------	-----------

A512 28-JAN-97 17:44:36 445 00 49.94 -3.35 AS P

HDS deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
10.	811.	6.0	171.	0.5	-10.5	129/12

GE DP

TWC DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A512 28-JAN-97 17:04:30 412 Ω 49.98 -5.81 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
125.	1035.	-0.6	159.	7.6	2.2	337/5

OZONE MR 41.01 PSAP LIN 0.12
ppb E-5m-1

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A512 28-JAN-97 15:58:12 308 Ω 53.37 -5.51 RY

HDG deg 177.	SPR mb 1005.	PHGT kft 0.2	TAS knots 158.	TAT C 5.7	DEW C 2.5	WIND deg 002/14
--------------------	--------------------	--------------------	----------------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------------

OZONE MR 38.51 PSAP LIN 0.05
ppb E-5m-1

A B C D E F G H
SELECT PARAS FREQ ZOOM VIDEO HELP

A512 28-JAN-97 15:32:09 288 Ω 54.72 -5.39 RV P

HDG degT 148.	SPR mb 1038.	PHGT kft -0.7	TAS knots 163.	TAT C 8.0	DEW C 4.3	WIND deg m/s 324/14
---------------------	--------------------	---------------------	----------------------	-----------------	-----------------	---------------------------

OZONE MR 40.25 PSAP LIN 0.00
ppb E-5m-1

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A512 28-JAN-97 15:25:03 281 -- 55.02 -5.71 AS P/

HQG deg	SPR ms	PHGT kms	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg
148.	1038.	-0.7	158.	7.6	5.0	317/11

SE IF

0

-10

-30

500 -30

TWC IF

-20

10

300

300

1000

30

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A512

28-JAN-97

14:01:48

209 Ω

55.75

0.23 RV P

HDG degT 340.	SPR mb 1036.	PHGT kft -0.6	TAS knots 168.	TAT C 7.4	DEW C 4.7	WIND deg m/s 222/4
---------------------	--------------------	---------------------	----------------------	-----------------	-----------------	--------------------------

OZONE MR
ppb

34.73

PSAP LIN
E-5m-1

0.22

52.50

0.63

50.00

0.50

37.50

0.38

25.00

0.25

12.50

0.13

0.00

0.00

A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
-------------	------------	-----------	-----------	---	---	------------	-----------

A512 28-JAN-97 13:56:03 206 Ω 55.48 0.42 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
339.	1037.	-0.6	173.	7.4	4.6	209/3

OZONE MR 34.41 PSSP LIN 0.24
pps E-5m-1

0.50
0.50
0.50
0.50
0.15
0.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A512 28-JAN-97 13:36:27 185 Ω 54.57 0.82 RV P

HDG degt 345.	SPR mb 987.	PHGT kft 0.7	TAS knots 164.	TAT C 4.8	DEW C 2.8	WIND deg 092 / 4
---------------------	-------------------	--------------------	----------------------	-----------------	-----------------	------------------------

OZONE NR 40.47 ESR LIN 0.05
 PPR 62.50 E-5m-1

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A512 28-JAN-97 12:56:57 143 -- 52.86 2.31 AS P

MODE	REF	PHGT	TRF	TAT	DEW	WIND
deg	ft	ft	cross	C	C	deg m/s
326.	812.	6.0	196.	-3.2	-10.8	101/ 8

SE EF

0

-10

-20

-30

400

TIME EF

500

10

600

800

1000

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A512 28-JAN-97 12:47:09 133 Ω 52.44 2.61 RV F

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
17.	1004.	0.3	163.	5.1	1.6	186/5

OZONE MR 39.12 PSAP LIN 0.04
ppb E-5m-1

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A512 28-JAN-97 12:10:09 093 Ω 50.87 1.28 RV

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
43.	1013.	0.0	176.	4.6	0.4	128 / 3

CZONE MR 35.75 ESSE LIN 0.07
 155.00 E-5m-1

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VTDF0		HFIP

A512 28-JAN-97 11:55:57 079 Ω 50.43 0.47 RV P

HDG deg T 58.	SPR mb 1014.	PHGT kft 0.0	TAS knts 171.	TAT C 3.9	DEW C 2.9	WIND deg m/s 311 / 2
---------------------	--------------------	--------------------	---------------------	-----------------	-----------------	----------------------------

OZONE MR 29.13 PSAP LIN 0.32
 PPB E-5m-1

1.25
 1.00
 0.75
 0.50
 0.25
 0.00

1130 1135 1140 1145 1150 1155

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM	VIDEO	HELP		

ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 0000 UTC 28 JAN 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection. Standard Parallel 60°N. Original scale 1:20m

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:20m

Prepared and drawn to the Cartographic Section, Met.O. Coll., Bracknell
Met.O. Coll. Form 11/288
Amended July 1990

FORM 11/288
Met.O. Coll. Form 11/288
Amended July 1990

SCALE OF NAUTICAL MILES

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR 4 MB INTERVALS

28 JAN '97 16:07

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:20m

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FORM 1000 (REVISED 1986) (CIP 215 98 0001 1150)

FRCIT 4-UP
28 JAN '97 13:46

12Z 28 JAN 1997

MET-OFFICE-ARTIFAX-2 PAGE. 002

LERWICK
03005
AT 11Z

10	300	40
15	290	37
20	280	50
25	270	50
30	275	49
40	280	48
50	289	47
60	300	41
70	300	33
85	320	24
100		
MAX	NIL	
TROP	181	-72
	270	50
10	1607	
15	1354	
20	1181	
25	1064	
30	927	
40	732	
50	572	
70	315	
85	161	
100	29	
10	233.0	
15	173.0	
20	137.0	
25	117.0	
30	103.0	
40	150.0	
50	257.2	
60	286.1	
70	311.8	
85	543.3	
100		
10	-61	
15	-62	
20	-69	

UCCLE
06447
AT 11Z

10	335	10
15	030	21
20	075	47
25	065	78
30	065	66
40	060	60
50	060	51
60	055	39
70	050	29
85	060	17
100	050	16
MAX	10615	
TROP	183	-65
	070	35
10	1616	
15	1359	
20	1181	
25	1042	
30	926	
40	732	
50	572	
70	315	
85	161	
100	32	
10	257.0	
15	178.0	
20	139.0	
25	116.0	
30	104.0	
40	160.0	
50	257.1	
60	282.9	
70	311.8	
85	540.3	
100		
10	-58	
15	-61	
20	-61	

DE BILT
06260

10	350	21
15	030	19
20	065	54
25	065	62
30	065	58
40	055	49
50	045	41
60	035	35
70	025	27
85	010	16
100	010	10
MAX	11058	
TROP	207	-67
	060	62
10	1613	
15	1358	
20	1182	
25	1045	
30	928	
40	731	
50	573	
70	315	
85	162	
100	32	
10	255.0	
15	178.0	
20	137.0	
25	117.0	
30	104.0	
40	161.0	
50	258.1	
60	282.8	
70	311.8	
85	541.2	
100		
10	-58	
15	-60	
20	-66	

**STORNOWAY
03026
AT 11Z**

10	255	16
15	265	28
20	260	36
25	255	36
30	250	36
40	255	28
50	260	31
60	265	30
70	275	24
85	270	10
100		
MAX	NIL	
TROP	196	-71
	240	37
10	1612	
15	1359	
20	1186	
25	1049	
30	932	
40	738	
50	577	
70	320	
85	165	
100	34	
M	253.0	
M	173.0	
M	137.0	
M	117.0	
M	194.0	
M	161.0	
M	257.5	
M	285.5	
M	130.7	
M	543.0	
10	-36	
15	-63	
20	-69	

**VALENTIA
03953**

10	305	12
15	325	6
20	140	33
25	120	37
30	135	29
40	135	23
50	130	16
60	130	10
70	110	12
85	090	12
100	070	6
MAX	NIL	
TROP	193	-67
	145	25
10	1621	
15	1386	
20	1189	
25	1051	
30	935	
40	740	
50	580	
70	322	
85	166	
100	35	
M	253.0	
M	177.0	
M	138.0	
M	116.0	
M	195.0	
M	160.0	
M	258.5	
M	286.5	
M	131.5	
M	545.0	
10	-59	
15	-59	
20	-66	

**BOULMER
03240
AT 11Z**

10	305	14
15	315	19
20	030	13
25	260	4
30	135	3
40	355	12
50	335	16
60	345	16
70	350	16
85	015	13
100		
MAX	NIL	
TROP	182	-72
	085	5
10	1614	
15	1361	
20	1188	
25	1051	
30	935	
40	739	
50	579	
70	321	
85	165	
100	34	
M	253.0	
M	173.0	
M	137.0	
M	116.0	
M	195.0	
M	160.0	
M	258.5	
M	286.7	
M	130.6	
M	545.0	
10	-59	
15	-63	
20	-69	

**LONG KESH
03920
AT 11Z**

10	265	12
15	290	11
20	135	20
25	165	12
30	195	9
40	200	12
50	175	10
60	170	5
70	115	9
85	025	6
100		
MAX	NIL	
TROP	200	-69
	135	20
10	1617	
15	1363	
20	1189	
25	1052	
30	936	
40	741	
50	580	
70	322	
85	166	
100	36	
M	253.0	
M	174.0	
M	137.0	
M	116.0	
M	195.0	
M	161.0	
M	258.1	
M	286.1	
M	130.7	
M	544.5	
10	-59	
15	-61	
20	-69	

FACIT 4-UP
28 JAN '97 13:44

12Z 28 JAN 1997

01 00Z TUES 28/ 1/97 VI 00Z TUES 28/ 1/97 GMAIN 1+ 0 - - - THICKNESS DM. 500-1000MB 500MB

28 JAN '97 03:59

DIAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03:30:55

CHART 27

PHDA30 EGRR 00007

1 002 LUES 28/ 1/97 VI 002 LUES 28/ 1/97

GMATN 1+ 0

HEIGHT DM.

300NB

28 JAN '97 04:03

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_1 PAGE.001

11 00Z TUES 28/ 1/97 VI 00Z WED 29/ 1/97 GRAIN T + 24 HEIGHT DM. 300MB

MET-OFFICE-ARTIFAX_4 PAGE.001

28 JAN . 97 03:55

OLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.38.39 CHART 27 PHDE30 EGRR 0000Z

SNOW PROBABILITY AT MSL
 TOTAL PPN RATE AT MSL

0.03
 0.05
 0.1
 0.15
 0.2
 0.3
 0.4
 0.5
 0.6
 0.7
 0.8
 0.9
 1.0

MM/HR AT VT
 *
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01 12Z TUESDAY 28/1/1997
 01 18Z TUESDAY 28/1/1997
 01 12Z WEDNESDAY 29/1/1997

01 12Z TUESDAY 28/1/1997
 01 18Z WEDNESDAY 29/1/1997
 01 12Z WEDNESDAY 29/1/1997

01 18Z WEDNESDAY 28/1/1997
 01 18Z THURSDAY 30/1/1997

TOTAL ACCUMULATION
350MB WET BULB POT TEMP

01 12Z

TUESDAY

28/1/1997

LMAIN

U=00-44 V=5-9 N=50-56 X=55-59 Y=60-64 Z=65 AND OVER

Meteosat-IR_280197_11:00CMT

Level 2 28/01/97

From 15Z 26/ 1/1997 to 18Z 28/ 1/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

Level 3 28/01/97

From 15Z 26/ 1/1997 to 18Z 28/ 1/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

Level 5 28/01/97

From 15Z 26/ 1/1997 to 18Z 28/ 1/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

A512 28-JAN-97 10:49:00-18:11:00GMT

A512 28-JAN-97 Height time series

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. A512

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 23826
Mean -1.57467
Standard dev 65.7257
Max value 100.657
Min value -155.664

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 23826
Mean 282.086
Standard dev 2.60230
Max value 288.625
Min value 273.706

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 23826
Mean 278.200
Standard dev 2.45758
Max value 281.522
Min value 269.795

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. A512

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 23826
Mean 282.257
Standard dev 2.60993
Max value 288.795
Min value 273.795

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 23826
Mean 278.253
Standard dev 2.47592
Max value 281.619
Min value 269.775

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 23826
Mean 278.326
Standard dev 2.68507
Max value 282.409
Min value 268.694

1 second overages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. A512

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 23826
Mean 4.22370
Standard dev 0.839660
Max value 8.80196
Min value 0.384318

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 23826
Mean 274.134
Standard dev 4.02217
Max value 279.159
Min value 254.835

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 23826
Mean 274.002
Standard dev 4.36522
Max value 280.514
Min value 242.901

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. A512

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 23826
Mean 0.132227
Standard dev 3.598699e-02
Max value 0.714507
Min value 3.094981e-02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 23826
Mean 980.819
Standard dev 77.5498
Max value 1039.36
Min value 807.240

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 23826
Mean 50.2761
Standard dev 14.2375
Max value 116.796
Min value 29.4987

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. A512

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 23826
Mean 209.095
Standard dev 124.360
Max value 648.394
Min value 53.5863

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 23826
Mean 103.513
Standard dev 63.1612
Max value 357.799
Min value 25.8570

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 23826
Mean 1025.51
Standard dev 30.7863
Max value 1049.50
Min value 643.648

1 second averages

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P1

Times 11:07:08-11:19:04 GMT

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P1

Times 11:07:08-11:19:04 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

1 second averages

1 second averages

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P2

Times 11:20:09-11:23:51 GMT

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P2

Times 11:20:09-11:23:51 GMT

1 second averages
Parameter no. 736
Parameter no. 519
Parameter no. 520

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P2

Times 11:20:09-11:23:51 GMT

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P2

Times 11:20:09-11:23:51 GMT

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P2

Times 11:20:09-11:23:51 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

1 second averages

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P3

Times 11:25:27 - 11:26:33 GMT

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P3

Times 11:25:27-11:26:33 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

1 second averages

1 second averages

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P4

Times 12:42:15-12:54:42 GMT

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P4

Times 12:42:15-12:54:42 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P5

Times 13:01:55-13:07:29 GMT

1 second averages

Parameter no. 730

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 735

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P5

Times 13:01:55-13:07:29 GMT

1 second averages

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P5

Times 13:01:55 - 13:07:29 GMT

1 second averages
Parameter no. 535

Parameter no. 577

Parameter no. 574

1 second averages

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P6

Times 13:29:42-13:42:18 GMT

1 second averages

1 second averages

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P7

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P7

Times 14:07:24-14:16:03 GMT

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P7

Times 14:07:24-14:16:03 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 520

Parameter no. 519

Parameter no. 736

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P7

Times 14:07:24-14:16:03 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P7

Times 14:07:24-14:16:03 GMT

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P7

Times 14:07:24-14:16:03 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P8

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P8

Times 15:08:46 - 15:19:47 GMT

1 second averages

1 second averages

1 second averages

1 second averages

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P9

Times 15:53:47-16:06:21 GMT

1 second averages

Times 15:53:47 - 16:06:21 GMT

A512 28--JAN-97 Profile P9

1857

1341

826

310

-206

-200

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736

1 second averages

245

275

305

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519

245

275

305

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520

A512 28--JAN--97 Profile P10

Times 17:27:28--17:44:17 GMT

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P10

Times 17:27:28-17:44:17 GMT

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P10

Times 17:27:28-17:44:17 GMT

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97 Profile P10

Times 17:27:28 - 17:44:17 GMT

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R10

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 557
Mean 97.1751
Standard dev 6.14338
Max value 111.586
Min value 88.9441

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 557
Mean 15.7701
Standard dev 1.09225
Max value 18.1013
Min value 13.5314

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 557
Mean north 2.04672
Stan dev north 1.86648
Max north 6.51274
Min north -0.262222
Mean east 2.04672
Stan dev east 1.86648
Max east 6.51274
Min east -0.262222

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R10

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 557
Mean -110.611
Standard dev 2.51084
Max value -104.668
Min value -114.013

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 557
Mean 281.125
Standard dev 0.583832
Max value 281.962
Min value 280.213

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 557
Mean 276.708
Standard dev 0.498159
Max value 277.431
Min value 275.749

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R10

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 557
Mean 281.281
Standard dev 0.590760
Max value 282.128
Min value 280.353

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 557
Mean 276.731
Standard dev 0.504329
Max value 277.459
Min value 275.755

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 557
Mean 272.219
Standard dev 1.30815
Max value 277.860
Min value 270.840

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R10

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 557
Mean 3.06740
Standard dev 0.175002
Max value 3.50823
Min value 2.85239

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 557
Mean 267.889
Standard dev 0.722818
Max value 269.538
Min value 267.114

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 557
Mean 267.410
Standard dev 0.744033
Max value 269.252
Min value 266.462

14:58:11 15:00:30 15:02:49 15:05:08 15:07:27
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R10

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 557
Mean 1853.15
Standard dev 7.23512
Max value 1859.52
Min value 1824.94

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 557
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 557
Mean 43.1937
Standard dev 0.699772
Max value 45.2656
Min value 41.3799

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R11

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 1449
Mean 213.266
Standard dev 153.882
Max value 359.972
Min value 0.316525

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 1449
Mean 13.9196
Standard dev 1.51326
Max value 17.3662
Min value 10.9868

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 1449
Mean north -12.5217
Stan dev north 2.42291
Max north -8.59141
Min north -17.1723
Mean east -12.5217
Stan dev east 2.42291
Max east -8.59141
Min east -17.1723

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R11

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 1449
Mean 22.9566
Standard dev 34.0663
Max value 53.6573
Min value -35.1601

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 1449
Mean 284.331
Standard dev 0.257090
Max value 284.836
Min value 283.688

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 1449
Mean 281.020
Standard dev 0.172015
Max value 281.374
Min value 280.652

15:21:06 15:27:08 15:33:10 15:39:12 15:45:14
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R11

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 1449
Mean 284.513
Standard dev 0.260249
Max value 285.037
Min value 283.858

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 1449
Mean 281.100
Standard dev 0.172122
Max value 281.459
Min value 280.737

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 1449
Mean 280.300
Standard dev 0.277469
Max value 280.870
Min value 279.681

15:21:06 15:27:08 15:33:10 15:39:12 15:45:14
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R11

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 1449
Mean 5.03046
Standard dev 0.156926
Max value 5.45850
Min value 4.40023

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 1449
Mean 277.626
Standard dev 0.420178
Max value 278.705
Min value 275.819

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 1449
Mean 277.592
Standard dev 0.444852
Max value 278.762
Min value 275.696

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R11

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 1449
Mean 0.123693
Standard dev 4.225105e-03
Max value 0.148339
Min value 9.335083e-02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 1449
Mean 1037.27
Standard dev 0.775299
Max value 1038.45
Min value 1031.11

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 1449
Mean 45.4357
Standard dev 1.73450
Max value 52.3910
Min value 40.1972

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R11

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1449
Mean -198.011
Standard dev 6.33799
Max value -147.607
Min value -205.969

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1449
Mean 33.0962
Standard dev 5.97323
Max value 81.2372
Min value 25.4816

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 1449
Mean 39.1285
Standard dev 1.57818
Max value 42.8512
Min value 32.6424

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R12

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 89
Mean 42.7204
Standard dev 1.40842
Max value 45.0992
Min value 38.3213

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 89
Mean 15.4561
Standard dev 0.566225
Max value 16.2066
Min value 14.0345

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 89
Mean north -11.3508
Stan dev north 0.469103
Max north -10.5692
Min north -12.0884
Mean east -11.3508
Stan dev east 0.469103
Max east -10.5692
Min east -12.0884

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R12

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 89
Mean -13.3507
Standard dev 1.77677
Max value -7.48129
Min value -15.1270

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 89
Mean 278.551
Standard dev 0.156480
Max value 278.877
Min value 278.305

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 89
Mean 274.393
Standard dev 0.126243
Max value 274.614
Min value 274.175

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R12

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 89
Mean 278.692
Standard dev 0.163213
Max value 279.036
Min value 278.435

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 89
Mean 274.407
Standard dev 0.137163
Max value 274.646
Min value 274.169

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 89
Mean 278.421
Standard dev 3.467606e-02
Max value 278.504
Min value 278.314

16:06:21 16:06:43 16:07:05 16:07:27 16:07:49
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R12

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 89
Mean 2.83383
Standard dev 5.604926e-02
Max value 2.97620
Min value 2.77954

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 89
Mean 266.934
Standard dev 6.659424e-02
Max value 267.025
Min value 266.798

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 89
Mean 266.407
Standard dev 0.246605
Max value 267.032
Min value 266.163

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R12

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 89
Mean 0.137530
Standard dev 9.622635e-03
Max value 0.179451
Min value 9.552181e-02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 89
Mean 810.935
Standard dev 0.684847
Max value 811.374
Min value 808.677

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 89
Mean 45.8898
Standard dev 1.66998
Max value 48.2168
Min value 43.1910

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R12

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 89
Mean 1839.34
Standard dev 6.83234
Max value 1861.87
Min value 1834.97

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 89
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 89
Mean 42.6341
Standard dev 1.09012
Max value 44.7797
Min value 39.3805

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R13

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 4519
Mean 71.2285
Standard dev 111.726
Max value 360.000
Min value 4.449189e-02

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 4519
Mean 9.30648
Standard dev 4.02608
Max value 15.5347
Min value 0.191606

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 4519
Mean north -8.27593
Stan dev north 3.61733
Max north 0.722572
Min north -13.7126
Mean east -8.27593
Stan dev east 3.61733
Max east 0.722572
Min east -13.7126

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R13

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 4519
Mean 17.9530
Standard dev 40.2027
Max value 82.2749
Min value -23.3553

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 4519
Mean 284.066
Standard dev 0.337397
Max value 285.166
Min value 283.320

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 4519
Mean 280.669
Standard dev 0.274631
Max value 281.339
Min value 280.015

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R13

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 4519
Mean 284.248
Standard dev 0.338686
Max value 285.372
Min value 283.489

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 4519
Mean 280.747
Standard dev 0.276364
Max value 281.422
Min value 280.079

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 4519
Mean 281.099
Standard dev 0.689224
Max value 282.409
Min value 279.479

16:12:10 16:30:59 16:49:49 17:08:38 17:27:28
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R13

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 4519
Mean 4.67721
Standard dev 0.425059
Max value 5.51836
Min value 3.77779

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 4519
Mean 276.320
Standard dev 1.27372
Max value 278.737
Min value 273.485

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 4519
Mean 276.484
Standard dev 1.30997
Max value 278.903
Min value 273.537

1 second averages

16:12:10 16:30:59 16:49:49 17:08:38 17:27:28
TIME (GMT)

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R13

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 4519
Mean 0.123830
Standard dev 6.863657e-03
Max value 0.156673
Min value 9.204040e-02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 4519
Mean 1035.13
Standard dev 1.27579
Max value 1037.43
Min value 1030.16

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 4519
Mean 46.6015
Standard dev 2.86692
Max value 54.4503
Min value 38.5883

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R13

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 4519
Mean -180.526
Standard dev 10.4398
Max value -139.806
Min value -199.341

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 4519
Mean 34.6680
Standard dev 4.46660
Max value 68.4134
Min value 25.4816

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 4519
Mean 29.3185
Standard dev 7.60792
Max value 43.2049
Min value 8.96445

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R7

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 784
Mean 209.586
Standard dev 5.99863
Max value 232.900
Min value 194.803

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 784
Mean 4.81169
Standard dev 0.704753
Max value 6.58909
Min value 2.84838

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 784
Mean north 4.16112
Stan dev north 0.655777
Max north 5.81930
Min north 2.28934
Mean east 4.16112
Stan dev east 0.655777
Max east 5.81930
Min east 2.28934

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R7

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 784
Mean -25.9177
Standard dev 6.36494
Max value -12.8696
Min value -35.8557

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 784
Mean 284.141
Standard dev 0.151484
Max value 284.608
Min value 283.857

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 784
Mean 280.489
Standard dev 4.600787e-02
Max value 280.616
Min value 280.375

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R7

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 784
Mean 284.322
Standard dev 0.155241
Max value 284.806
Min value 284.031

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 784
Mean 280.558
Standard dev 4.834526e-02
Max value 280.693
Min value 280.435

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 784
Mean 278.647
Standard dev 0.121571
Max value 278.939
Min value 278.393

13:51:54 13:55:09 13:58:25 14:01:41 14:04:57
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R7

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 784
Mean 5.11699
Standard dev 8.756945e-02
Max value 5.29842
Min value 4.83273

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 784
Mean 277.782
Standard dev 0.192481
Max value 278.202
Min value 277.084

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 784
Mean 277.822
Standard dev 0.243376
Max value 278.317
Min value 277.022

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R7

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 784
Mean 0.120240
Standard dev 5.417197e-03
Max value 0.146672
Min value 9.359708e-02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 784
Mean 1036.01
Standard dev 0.405172
Max value 1036.93
Min value 1034.22

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 784
Mean 50.2311
Standard dev 2.16560
Max value 56.2877
Min value 46.5182

1 second overages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R7

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 784
Mean -187.737
Standard dev 3.31318
Max value -173.107
Min value -195.296

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 784
Mean 33.3623
Standard dev 2.65995
Max value 46.6688
Min value 27.7119

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 784
Mean 34.4358
Standard dev 2.56298
Max value 39.3709
Min value 17.9118

13:51:54 13:55:09 13:58:25 14:01:41 14:04:57
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R8

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 362
Mean 54.4088
Standard dev 5.78373
Max value 68.6041
Min value 33.7941

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 362
Mean 4.67361
Standard dev 0.503882
Max value 6.05596
Min value 3.57140

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 362
Mean north -2.69223
Stan dev north 0.390185
Max north -1.62529
Min north -3.79836
Mean east -2.69223
Stan dev east 0.390185
Max east -1.62529
Min east -3.79836

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R8

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 362
Mean -87.3199
Standard dev 1.80766
Max value -83.1577
Min value -90.5767

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 362
Mean 283.576
Standard dev 0.208440
Max value 283.882
Min value 283.069

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 362
Mean 280.169
Standard dev 6.618200e-02
Max value 280.328
Min value 280.019

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R8

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 362
Mean 283.758
Standard dev 0.211017
Max value 284.061
Min value 283.241

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 362
Mean 280.247
Standard dev 6.443657e-02
Max value 280.394
Min value 280.102

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 362
Mean 279.122
Standard dev 0.105046
Max value 279.430
Min value 278.896

14:19:37 14:21:07 14:22:37 14:24:07 14:25:38
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R8

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 362
Mean 4.80498
Standard dev 0.111097
Max value 5.13359
Min value 4.45815

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 362
Mean 276.845
Standard dev 0.330483
Max value 277.603
Min value 275.876

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 362
Mean 276.945
Standard dev 0.327285
Max value 277.887
Min value 275.891

14:19:37 14:21:07 14:22:37 14:24:07 14:25:38
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R8

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 362
Mean 0.121365
Standard dev 7.694774e-03
Max value 0.140079
Min value 6.422238e-02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 362
Mean 1037.27
Standard dev 0.217666
Max value 1037.73
Min value 1036.75

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 362
Mean 46.9232
Standard dev 2.34108
Max value 50.4509
Min value 41.1821

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R8

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 362
Mean -198.058
Standard dev 1.77808
Max value -193.832
Min value -201.797

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 362
Mean 31.0089
Standard dev 1.81854
Max value 36.2610
Min value 26.9684

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 362
Mean 28.1275
Standard dev 1.41033
Max value 30.9123
Min value 24.5614

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R9

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 595
Mean 57.8310
Standard dev 2.39651
Max value 72.2689
Min value 43.4840

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 595
Mean 15.5572
Standard dev 0.759250
Max value 17.6701
Min value 13.0557

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 595
Mean north -8.27845
Stan dev north 0.724112
Max north -4.22874
Min north -12.8208
Mean east -8.27845
Stan dev east 0.724112
Max east -4.22874
Min east -12.8208

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R9

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 595
Mean -105.477
Standard dev 2.89933
Max value -99.0638
Min value -121.507

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 595
Mean 281.578
Standard dev 0.471139
Max value 283.631
Min value 280.614

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 595
Mean 277.436
Standard dev 0.342499
Max value 278.019
Min value 276.392

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R9

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 595
Mean 281.748
Standard dev 0.476154
Max value 283.869
Min value 280.758

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 595
Mean 277.480
Standard dev 0.346317
Max value 278.080
Min value 276.408

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 595
Mean 276.571
Standard dev 1.08666
Max value 279.356
Min value 273.409

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R9

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 595
Mean 3.24033
Standard dev 8.886621e-02
Max value 3.45817
Min value 3.05347

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 595
Mean 268.732
Standard dev 0.339723
Max value 269.416
Min value 268.136

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 595
Mean 268.159
Standard dev 0.374984
Max value 269.034
Min value 267.347

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R9

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 595
Mean 0.116317
Standard dev 8.655517e-03
Max value 0.197582
Min value 6.447668e-02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 595
Mean 810.121
Standard dev 1.00657
Max value 811.609
Min value 807.727

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 595
Mean 45.1510
Standard dev 3.30767
Max value 64.8307
Min value 39.5939

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R9

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 595
Mean 1847.46
Standard dev 10.0426
Max value 1871.37
Min value 1832.62

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 595
Mean 179.076
Standard dev 490.833
Max value 1522.15
Min value 0.000000

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 595
Mean 40.5075
Standard dev 1.63550
Max value 44.9159
Min value 36.7185

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R4

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 1250
Mean 192.647
Standard dev 24.0092
Max value 287.886
Min value 136.048

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 1250
Mean 4.26632
Standard dev 1.23725
Max value 8.97991
Min value 1.73642

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 1250
Mean north 3.70030
Stan dev north 1.48872
Max north 6.68367
Min north -1.92558
Mean east 3.70030
Stan dev east 1.48872
Max east 6.68367
Min east -1.92558

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R4

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 1250
Mean 37.1726
Standard dev 11.5604
Max value 81.5202
Min value 11.3673

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 1250
Mean 280.485
Standard dev 0.805061
Max value 281.960
Min value 278.855

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 1250
Mean 276.956
Standard dev 0.838903
Max value 278.362
Min value 274.873

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R4

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 1250
Mean 280.650
Standard dev 0.817299
Max value 282.130
Min value 278.853

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 1250
Mean 277.013
Standard dev 0.863240
Max value 278.413
Min value 274.677

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 1250
Mean 275.117
Standard dev 0.963410
Max value 276.806
Min value 273.274

12:18:43 12:23:55 12:29:07 12:34:19 12:39:32
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R4

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 1250
Mean 4.49122
Standard dev 0.322356
Max value 8.80196
Min value 3.89608

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 1250
Mean 275.714
Standard dev 0.791069
Max value 277.092
Min value 273.704

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 1250
Mean 275.512
Standard dev 1.11654
Max value 280.514
Min value 273.017

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R4

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 1250
Mean 0.180758
Standard dev 9.041723e-02
Max value 0.664918
Min value 9.517577e-02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 1250
Mean 1004.66
Standard dev 18.1408
Max value 1032.80
Min value 964.947

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 1250
Mean 47.5992
Standard dev 5.09523
Max value 58.9929
Min value 37.2450

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R4

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1250
Mean 72.9135
Standard dev 153.011
Max value 410.067
Min value -161.463

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1250
Mean 279.148
Standard dev 149.776
Max value 610.358
Min value 49.8282

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 1250
Mean 36.3891
Standard dev 2.39114
Max value 41.8595
Min value 29.7992

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R5

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 434
Mean 98.0496
Standard dev 8.60885
Max value 113.795
Min value 80.0287

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 434
Mean 8.03607
Standard dev 0.552667
Max value 9.13267
Min value 7.04022

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 434
Mean north 1.14424
Stan dev north 1.25447
Max north 3.58959
Min north -1.38063
Mean east 1.14424
Stan dev east 1.25447
Max east 3.58959
Min east -1.38063

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R5

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 434
Mean -62.3493
Standard dev 2.11382
Max value -53.4782
Min value -65.8011

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 434
Mean 275.372
Standard dev 0.622112
Max value 276.709
Min value 273.874

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 434
Mean 270.651
Standard dev 0.561614
Max value 271.762
Min value 269.795

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R5

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 434
Mean 275.507
Standard dev 0.634346
Max value 276.874
Min value 273.971

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 434
Mean 270.643
Standard dev 0.569353
Max value 271.774
Min value 269.775

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 434
Mean 275.041
Standard dev 6.453407e-02
Max value 275.236
Min value 274.850

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R5

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 434
Mean 2.09535
Standard dev 0.275394
Max value 2.56543
Min value 1.63101

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 434
Mean 263.610
Standard dev 1.50045
Max value 266.125
Min value 261.108

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 434
Mean 262.426
Standard dev 1.70060
Max value 265.120
Min value 259.388

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R5

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 434
Mean 0.136498
Standard dev 5.428375e-03
Max value 0.163139
Min value 9.719382e-02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 434
Mean 811.836
Standard dev 0.394843
Max value 813.071
Min value 811.130

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 434
Mean 53.0455
Standard dev 2.37289
Max value 56.4571
Min value 43.7332

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R5

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 434
Mean 1830.37
Standard dev 3.93268
Max value 1837.40
Min value 1818.07

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 434
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 434
Mean 44.5664
Standard dev 1.80764
Max value 49.1228
Min value 38.7847

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R6

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 850
Mean 76.1170
Standard dev 5.45878
Max value 94.6571
Min value 65.3018

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 850
Mean 7.55257
Standard dev 0.408051
Max value 8.49440
Min value 6.59026

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 850
Mean north -1.78222
Stan dev north 0.652297
Max north 0.606773
Min north -2.97797
Mean east -1.78222
Stan dev east 0.652297
Max east 0.606773
Min east -2.97797

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R6

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 850
Mean -58.5645
Standard dev 1.61428
Max value -51.8401
Min value -62.4778

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 850
Mean 282.259
Standard dev 0.199714
Max value 282.812
Min value 281.471

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 850
Mean 278.234
Standard dev 7.792584e-02
Max value 278.369
Min value 277.973

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R6

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 850
Mean 282.431
Standard dev 0.199193
Max value 282.994
Min value 281.674

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 850
Mean 278.283
Standard dev 7.623827e-02
Max value 278.415
Min value 278.082

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 850
Mean 276.347
Standard dev 0.200687
Max value 276.818
Min value 276.021

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R6

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 850
Mean 4.35658
Standard dev 7.426537e-02
Max value 4.50630
Min value 4.15712

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 850
Mean 274.506
Standard dev 13.3409
Max value 275.593
Min value 0.000000

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 850
Mean 275.036
Standard dev 0.238777
Max value 275.512
Min value 274.380

1 second averages

13:07:29 13:11:01 13:14:33 13:18:05 13:21:08
TIME (GMT)

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R6

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 850
Mean 0.123329
Standard dev 4.455715e-03
Max value 0.151822
Min value 9.170120e-02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 850
Mean 998.592
Standard dev 0.350250
Max value 999.530
Min value 997.037

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 850
Mean 53.8897
Standard dev 2.67579
Max value 60.7614
Min value 46.3564

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R6

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 850
Mean 122.738
Standard dev 2.95102
Max value 135.842
Min value 114.833

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 850
Mean 339.900
Standard dev 3.47257
Max value 350.723
Min value 330.279

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 850
Mean 39.4140
Standard dev 1.12674
Max value 43.0421
Min value 35.7594

13:07:29 13:11:01 13:14:33 13:18:05 13:21:38

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R1

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 519
Mean 335.813
Standard dev 8.81825
Max value 359.714
Min value 311.266

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 519
Mean 5.43605
Standard dev 0.744951
Max value 7.75633
Min value 2.60479

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 519
Mean north -4.88840
Stan dev north 0.667592
Max north -2.42392
Min north -6.75496
Mean east -4.88840
Stan dev east 0.667592
Max east -2.42392
Min east -6.75496

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R1

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 519
Mean 82.9466
Standard dev 1.25809
Max value 85.0065
Min value 77.9098

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 519
Mean 280.457
Standard dev 0.146271
Max value 280.822
Min value 279.912

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 519
Mean 277.278
Standard dev 9.662589e-02
Max value 277.543
Min value 277.014

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R1

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 519
Mean 280.625
Standard dev 0.152418
Max value 280.995
Min value 280.053

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 519
Mean 277.350
Standard dev 9.855110e-02
Max value 277.617
Min value 277.075

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 519
Mean 279.832
Standard dev 0.107532
Max value 280.037
Min value 279.509

11:26:57 11:29:06 11:31:16 11:33:25 11:35:35
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R1

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 519
Mean 4.35358
Standard dev 0.136033
Max value 4.65830
Min value 3.97576

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 519
Mean 275.576
Standard dev 0.416315
Max value 276.500
Min value 274.482

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 519
Mean 275.218
Standard dev 0.442702
Max value 276.166
Min value 273.955

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R1

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 519
Mean 0.153165
Standard dev 1.125326e-02
Max value 0.189202
Min value 0.101299

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 519
Mean 1012.78
Standard dev 0.940092
Max value 1014.86
Min value 1010.55

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 519
Mean 43.1472
Standard dev 1.53345
Max value 46.7466
Min value 37.4089

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R1

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 519
Mean 3.88151
Standard dev 7.82964
Max value 22.4825
Min value -13.3637

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 519
Mean 210.104
Standard dev 7.52940
Max value 228.060
Min value 194.421

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 519
Mean 31.7007
Standard dev 2.22929
Max value 36.1902
Min value 26.4546

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R2

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 1409
Mean 169.641
Standard dev 105.072
Max value 359.894
Min value 0.225041

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 1409
Mean 1.50004
Standard dev 0.773786
Max value 3.93523
Min value 4.537942e-02

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 1409
Mean north -0.118481
Stan dev north 0.848373
Max north 2.89961
Min north -2.77790
Mean east -0.118481
Stan dev east 0.848373
Max east 2.89961
Min east -2.77790

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R2

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 1409
Mean 73.2728
Standard dev 3.74654
Max value 81.6199
Min value 64.1860

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 1409
Mean 281.132
Standard dev 0.208407
Max value 281.623
Min value 280.599

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 1409
Mean 277.298
Standard dev 0.156302
Max value 277.613
Min value 276.889

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R2

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 1409
Mean 281.300
Standard dev 0.212845
Max value 281.808
Min value 280.756

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 1409
Mean 277.349
Standard dev 0.157474
Max value 277.683
Min value 276.931

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 1409
Mean 278.622
Standard dev 0.787585
Max value 279.779
Min value 277.222

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R2

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 1409
Mean 4.43605
Standard dev 0.170285
Max value 4.97121
Min value 3.81169

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 1409
Mean 275.624
Standard dev 0.488918
Max value 276.662
Min value 273.882

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 1409
Mean 275.479
Standard dev 0.541320
Max value 276.748
Min value 273.379

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R2

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 1409
Mean 0.155111
Standard dev 8.143361e-03
Max value 0.186400
Min value 0.115662

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 1409
Mean 1013.05
Standard dev 0.406944
Max value 1014.79
Min value 1012.01

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 1409
Mean 52.2191
Standard dev 2.01409
Max value 58.0682
Min value 44.7213

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R2

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1409
Mean 1.68763
Standard dev 3.38835
Max value 10.3627
Min value -12.8233

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1409
Mean 206.653
Standard dev 3.25324
Max value 214.865
Min value 194.235

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 1409
Mean 30.9892
Standard dev 2.66291
Max value 37.3895
Min value 21.4166

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R3

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 861
Mean 177.910
Standard dev 41.1507
Max value 293.363
Min value 93.7223

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 861
Mean 2.19947
Standard dev 0.606348
Max value 3.81477
Min value 0.876887

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 861
Mean north 1.77623
Stan dev north 0.909960
Max north 3.76914
Min north -0.646744
Mean east 1.77623
Stan dev east 0.909960
Max east 3.76914
Min east -0.646744

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R3

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 861
Mean 61.1614
Standard dev 3.86595
Max value 65.9771
Min value 53.0133

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 861
Mean 281.537
Standard dev 0.181222
Max value 281.949
Min value 280.914

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 861
Mean 277.705
Standard dev 0.162838
Max value 277.990
Min value 276.897

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R3

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 861
Mean 281.707
Standard dev 0.185424
Max value 282.127
Min value 281.041

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 861
Mean 277.759
Standard dev 0.168451
Max value 278.050
Min value 276.902

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 861
Mean 276.685
Standard dev 0.360642
Max value 277.223
Min value 275.910

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R3

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 861
Mean 3.85727
Standard dev 0.205047
Max value 4.40190
Min value 3.51349

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 861
Mean 273.798
Standard dev 0.655577
Max value 275.293
Min value 272.780

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 861
Mean 273.527
Standard dev 0.732666
Max value 275.379
Min value 272.268

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R3

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 861
Mean 0.148804
Standard dev 3.400222e-03
Max value 0.169158
Min value 0.126966

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 861
Mean 1012.85
Standard dev 0.275567
Max value 1013.63
Min value 1012.32

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 861
Mean 52.0953
Standard dev 1.94144
Max value 55.6198
Min value 46.3018

1 second averages

A512 28-JAN-97

Run no. R3

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 861
Mean 3.30005
Standard dev 2.29511
Max value 7.72449
Min value -3.16451

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 861
Mean 209.061
Standard dev 2.37843
Max value 213.192
Min value 202.227

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 861
Mean 37.2532
Standard dev 2.04276
Max value 42.6387
Min value 31.3458

1 second averages

28/01/97

UK Trace Gas Flux Measurements

Sortie Objective:

To measure the flux of methane, carbon dioxide and nitrous oxide from the UK.

Location: United Kingdom coastal waters.

Weather: Anticyclonic, airflow must be such that air crossing the UK is not contaminated with pollutants from Eastern Europe, *i.e.* airflow ideally from West to East but air flow from North East to South west accepted.

Flight Pattern:

[1] Depart Lyneham/Boscombe Down and transit to initial way point Q
[2] Execute stepped profile from minimum safe altitude to the top of the boundary layer at 1000feet/min. Profile to be interrupted for short runs approx. 30 seconds) at levels to be decided.

(a) _____, (b) _____, (c) _____, (d) _____, (e) _____

[3] Return to 500 feet for straight and level bag filling run. Remain at this level for 60-70 nm.

[4] Repeat [2] and [3] until between way points V and K.

[5] Cross UK to way point G, continue sampling pattern.

[6] Return to Lyneham *via* way point Q.

Intensive sampling periods at 180 kts otherwise 190/5 kts.

SF26: Prof David Fowler (Institute of terrestrial Ecology - Edinburgh) and Dr Geraint Morgan (Open University)

TUES
28 JAN 97

10.30 → 18.30^{ish}

TDTRAJ_D970128.TXT

From 12Z 27/ 1/1997 to 18Z 28/ 1/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

ATTENTION - ANDREW KAYE

Set-out below is an update of the "tiger" waypoints in case we need them next week. If you are considering a night-stop in Leuchars or Turnhouse we will need to know early for clearance purposes.

For your consideration, Leuchars - via south coast - Leuchars takes approx 8hrs (still air) and Leuchars - via north coast - Leuchars takes approx 4hrs (still air). Transit to/from Leuchars will take approx 1hr 45mins.

If you wish to identify the points with letters (as per your brief) please let me know. My suggestion is as shown.

UPDATE OF "TIGER" WAYPOINTS

(* SIGNIFIES A CHANGE TO CO-ORDINATES)

(+ SIGNIFIES A NEW WAYPOINT)

				<u>Ident Letter</u>	
	T 1	N5026.0	W00501.7	ST MAWGAN TACAN	A
18	T 2	*N5119.0	W00530.0	BOUNDARY LFA2/LFA7	B
17	T 3	*N5210.6	W00530.0	BOUNDARY D201A	C
	T 4	*N5315.0	W00530.0	BOUNDARY D201B	D
16	T 4A	*N5326.2	W00530.0	BOUNDARY LFA7/LFA17	D1
15	T 5	*N5431.0	W00509.0	BOUNDARY LFA17/LFA16	E
14	T 5A	+N5507.7	W00546.0	BOUNDARY LFA16/LFA14	E1
13	T 6	N5545.0	W00640.0		F
12	T 7	N5650.0	W00720.0	5650.0N 0800.0	G
	T 8	N5745.0	W00635.0		H
	T 9	N5910.0	W00500.0		I
	T 9A	+N5930.0	W00300.0		I1
	T10	*N5925.0	W00136.0		J
	T11	*N5750.0	W00156.0		K
	T11A	*N5730.0	W00130.0		K1
11	T11B	*N5700.0	W00130.0		K2
10	T11C	N5600.0	E00030.0	BOUNDARY LFA14/LFA12	K3
9	T12	N5500.0	E00130.0	BOUNDARY LFA12/LFA11	L
8	T13	*N5353.0	E00107.0		M
7	T13A	+N5309.0	E00146.0	BOUNDARY LFA11/LFA5	M1
6	T14	*N5230.0	E00220.0	0243.0 0144.0	N
5	T15	*N5130.0	E00152.0	5111.0N	O
4	T16	N5040.0	E00100.0		P
3	T17	*N5000.0	W00032.0	BOUNDARY D059	Q
	T17A	+N5040.0	W00100.0	(ALTERNATE TO T17 - IF REQUIRED)	Q1
	T18	+N5000.0	W00142.2	BOUNDARY D049	R
2	T18A	*N5000.0	W00200.0	BOUNDARY LFA18/LFA2	R1
22	T19	*N5001.0	W00300.0		S
21	T19A	+N4947.0	W00317.0	BOUNDARY D004	S1
20	T20	*N4928.0	W00500.0	BOUNDARY D008A	T
19	T21	N5000.0	W00600.0		U

~~TO HAWAII RICHIE 01252 376588~~

~~HAWAII THIS IS OUR UNDESIRABLE FLIGHT ROUTE DO YOU GO AHEAD ANY PROBLEMS?~~

KEN

Flight Plan - 28 January 1997

Transit to south coast as convenient, descend to 500 ft (or lower) ASL straight and level. Maintain 500 ft altitude between profile ascents. ~~Transit across Scotland at minimum safe altitude.~~

FLIGHT AC12

10:30 start up

UK CH₄, N₂O FLUX STUDY (TIGER)

Date 28 Jan 97

Time 1245

Bag No	Event Marker	Time	Location	Altitude	Comments
184	24	1057	~ Lynher	6000	free trip to 18A
185	25	1059	S "	6000	"
186	26	11:00	Boswell	6000	"
187	27	11:02	Coast	6000	"
188	28	11:04	"	6000	"
189	32	1119	Tolva	50-100	100
183	33	1120	Tolva	100	100 Ridge 1
182	336	1120	"	500	500
181	337	1121	"	500	500
180	40	1122	"	1000	1000
179	41	1123	"	1000	1000
178	44	1124	"	1500	1500
177	45	1125	"	1500	1500
176	450	1127		700	R → Q 718 → 717
175	52	1128		700	718 → 717
174	53	1128		700	"
173	5?	?		700	"
172	54	1130		700	"
171	55	1131		700	"
151	56	1132		700	"
152	57	1133		700	"
153	58	1134		700	"
154	59	1134		700	due S Portsmouth "
					Ridge following by O U

UK CH₄, N₂O FLUX STUDY (TIGER)

Date 28/1/96

Time

(2)

Bag No	Event Marker	Time	Location	Altitude	Comments
160	66	1141			Run 2
155/16	67				25 min ↓ (q → p) T17 - T16
157	68	1142			"
158	69	1143			"
159	70	1144			"
160	71	1144			"
161	72	1145			"
162	73	1146			"
163	74	1146			"
164	75	1147			- Beachy head approx
165	76	1150			at base R2 (p → q) T16 - T15
166	77	1151			"
167	78	1151			"
168	79	1151			" just E of B head 'mid' channel
169	80	1201			"
170	81	1202			"
190	82	1202			"
191	83	1202			"
192	85	1203			"
193	87	1204			Run 2 hours approx! DNR R2
194	88	1205			"
195	89	1205			"
196	90	1206			"
197	91	1206			"
198	92	1207			DNR 1690 Run 2 shv

Σ

Bag No	Event Marker	Time	Location	Altitude	Comments
199	93	1209			Run 2 continues Dover str. L.
200	94	1210			
201	95	1212			
202	96	1213			
203	97				White Cliffs
204	98	1214			" "
205	99	1214			(double labear 'bag)
206	100				
207	101	1216			shd. in chm ~ 2000 ft ~
208	102	1217			
209	103	1217			continuous sample ↓ Run 3
210	104	1218			↓ Run 4
211	107	1219			
* 212	108	1220		700'	RPS!
* 221	109	1221		700	
222	110	1222		700	x height change ↓ 700 some dived.
223	111	1222		↓ 650	↓ 650
224	112	1224		650	
225	113	1225		550	in cloud
226	114	1226		550	height now
227	115	1227		400	Bad Valves
228	116	1228		400	← Thawed Ev
					Bottle filling out, ~500

cx

*
*

Bag No	Event Marker	Time	Location	Altitude	Comments
		1240		50-00 100	Profile No 2
229	24	1243		100	
230	25	1243		100	
261	26			500	100 → 500
262	29			500	500
263	30	1		54000 ⁵⁰	500
264	33	1246		1000	
265	34	1247		10000	
266	37	1248		1500	
267	38	1248		1500	EADJ
268	41	1254		6000	non heading W of J Lowest pt
269	42	1255		6000	off Norfolk
270	43	1256		6000	
				6000	3 free trap bottles for OU "
		1302	6000	→ 1000	Run 5 approx point M Lincolnshire
251	49	1307		~1000	Run 6
252	50	1309		1000	
253	51	1309		1000	
254	52	1310		1000	
255	53	1310		1000	
256	54	1311		1000	
257	55	1311		1000	
258	56	1312		1000	
259	57	1312		1000	
260	58	1313		1500	Run 6 just off Spenser road.

6

Bag No	Event Marker	Time	Location	Altitude	Comments
					approx L 65 V sampling at 1000'
				1000	
278	88	1345		1500	
279	89	1346		1500	bot! 'cibe!
280	90	1347		1000	
281	91	1348		1000	
282	93	1349		500	
283	95	1350		500	
284	98	1352		100	Run? ~ whistby ~
285	99	1352		"	
286	2000	1353		"	
287	202	1354		100	
288	204	1355		"	
289	205	1355		"	
290	206	1356		"	
291	207	1357		"	
292	208	1401			
293	209				
294	210	1402		100	
		1404		100	OU milt's list 3 bottles x 3 samples 100-600'

7

Bag No	Event Marker	Time	Location	Altitude	Comments
					Profile
				100	turn ~ Benwick on Tweed ~
295	217	1409		100	
296	218	1410		100	
297	221	1411		500	
298	222	1412		500	
299	225	1414		1000	
300	226	1414		1000	
241	22			1500	
242	220	1418		1500	? height ↓ 1500-1000
					Location for St Aibhs
243	232	1420		100	
244	233	1420		100	
245	234			100	
246	235			100	
247	236	1422		100	
248	237	1423		100	
249	238	1424		100	
		1425		100	OU sample photo

28 JAW

Plan Flight C
512

(9)

Bag No	Event Marker	Time	Location	Altitude	Comments
					PROFILE 1000'
505	264	1514		1500	ISUM - JURU 55.14/632
506	265	1515		1500	
507	267	1516		1000+	119 1500
508	269	1516		1000	
509	270	1517		1000	
510	273	1518		500	
511	274	1518		500	
512	277	1519	20	100	
X 528	278	1520		100	
				100	OUT 2 bottles Run 11
					mistake: waxes for warships!
529	282	1525		100	
530	283	1526		100	
531	284	1526		100	
532	285	1527		100	
533	286	1527		100	
534	287	1528		100	
535	288	1529		100	
537	289	1529		100	
538	289	1532		100	
513	290	1536		100	less waxes & samples 1/2 2 m
515	292	1537		100	
516	293	1538		100	
517	294	1541		100	
521	295			100	send o/Islo, man

UK CH₄, N₂O FLUX STUDY (TIGER)

Date 28-1-97

Time flux 512

10

Bag No	Event Marker	Time	Location	Altitude	Comments
				500	S of Isb 57mm
524	297			500	a couple of extra
525	298			500 1000	bags ← LU to 500'
					Profile os ~37m
526	301	1557		100	
527	302	1558		100	← clock times re event log
109	304	1556		500	
110	305	1557		500	
111	308	1558		1000	
112	309	1558		1000	bag No - take re-
113	312	1559		1500	
115	313	1600		1500	
116	316	1606		6000	
118	317	1607		6000	Moel De bog
				100'	Run 13
119	320			100	
120	321			100	
539	322			100	
540	323	1613	100	100	moel water
542	324	1615		100	
543	327	1619		100	OU bottles 2 off
544	328	1620		100	
544	329			100	

10
55
x

546

UK CH₄, N₂O FLUX STUDY (TIGER)

Date 28-1-97

Time 1620

11

Bag No	Event Marker	Time	Location	Altitude	Comments
547	330			100	
548	331	1621		100	
550	332	1621		100	
551	333	1622		100	
-2	334	1622		100	valve ?
3	335	1623		100	
4	336	1623		100	
5	337	1624		100	
6	338	1624		100	Pen-probes
x 8	339	1625		100	
10	340	1625		100	
11	341	1626		100	
12	342	1626		100	
13	343	1627		100	
14	344	1628		100	
15	345	1628		100	O ₃ dropping
16	346			100	Soil water
17	347			101	
19	348	1630		100	
20	349	1630		100	
		1632			OC - 2 bottles 100'
21	352	1634			
22	353	1634			
f 40	354	1635			
4	355	1635			

UK CH₄, N₂O FLUX STUDY (TIGER)

Date: 28-1-97 Time: 16.35

(12)

Bag No	Event Marker	Time	Location	Altitude	Comments
1010	356	1636		100	
1011	357	1637	Lushy	100	7
1012	358	1637		100	
1013	359	1638		100	
1014	360	1639		100	
1015	361	1639 ³⁹		100	
1016	362	1639		100	
1017	363	1639		100	
1018	364	1639		100	
1019	365	1640		100	
1020	366	1641		100	
1001	367	1641		100	
1002	368	1641		100	
1003	369	1641		100	
1004	370	1642		100	
1005	371	1643		100	
1006	372	1644		100	
1007	373	1644		100	
1008	374	1645		100	
1009	375	1645		100	
50	376	1646		100	
52	377	1646		100	
54	378	1647		100	
55	379	1647		100	
56	380	1647		100	

*

Bag No	Event Marker	Time	Location	Altitude	Comments
57	351	1649		100	
59	382	1649		100	
60	383	1649		100	
61	384	1650		100	
62	386	1650		100	
81	389	1652		100	on bottle sample ①
82	390	1653		100	
84	391	1653		100	
86	392	"		100	
87	393	1654		100	
89	394	1655		100	
90	395	1656		100	
91	397	1656		100	
92	398	1657		100	
93	399	1658		100	
95	400	1658		100	
96	401	1659		100	
97	402	1659		100	
99	403	1659		100	
100	404	1660		100	(100)
103	405	1700		100	
104	406	1701		100	
108	407	1701		100	
111	408	1702		100	

13

UK CH₄, N₂O FLUX STUDY (TIGER)

28-1-98

Date

Time

UK CH₄, N₂O FLUX STUDY (TIGER)

Date 28-1-97

Time 1700

14

Bag No	Event Marker	Time	Location	Altitude	Comments
122	409	1702		100	2mch end
* 63	410	1703		100	
64	411	1704		100	
* 66	412	1704		100	
68	413	1704		100	
69	414	1705		100	
70	41 3 4	1705		100	
* 76	41 3 5	1706		100	415
77	416	06		100	
78	417	1707		100	
79	418	1707		100	
* 25	419	1709		100	clean air
26	420	1710		100	
27	421	1713		100	
28	422	1717		100	
29	423	1721		100	
* 37	424	1725		100	1725
38	425	1729		100	air dirty again
39	428	1728		5000	profile
* 42	429	1729		400500	
43	430	1730		400500	
1020	431	1730		500	
1021	432	1731		500	
1022	433	1732		500	
1023	434	1732		500	at Saxham midday

1733

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 512

DATE: 27/1/97

Take off: 1050

Landing: 1810

Aircraft Scientist : A. KAYE
Flight Leader : T. RILEY
Others BHP : M. RILEY
BAG FILMER : D. AMLEY
D. TIDELMAN
SPEC : D. FOWLER
G. BULLOCK

Captain : C. O'BRIEN
Co-pilot : L. PUNSE
Navigator : J. CANNING
Engineer : K. QUICK
Loadmaster : K. CROSS

Trials Instructions : MILITARY : MENTANE FLORIS

Operating area : ROAD UK

General synoptic situation

TIME :

A512 28th January, 1997
 NERC Methane profiling
 Round UK

Start time	End time	Event	Height	Hdg	Comments
104903					Take off from Lyneham
110708	111344	P1.1	6000'-500'	180	
111749	111904	P1.2	500'-50'	085	
112009	112038	P2.1	100'-500'		
112142	112211	P2.2	500'-1000'		
112329	112351	P2.3	1000'-1500'		
112527	112633	P3.1	1500'-700'		
112657	113535	R1	700'	090	
113954	120322	R2	700'	058	
120400	121820	R3	700'	050	
121843	123932	R4	700'-2000'	030	
124215	124258	P4.1	50'-100'		
124400	124431	P4.2	100-500'		
124551	124625	P4.3	500'-1000'		
124739	124803	P4.4	1000'-1500'		
124948	125442	P4.5	1500'-FL60		
125442	130155	R5	FL60	330	
130155	130729	P5	FL60-1000'	330	
130729	132138	R6	1000'	330	
132942	133004	P6.1	50'-100'	355	
133118	133148	P6.2	100'-500'		
133242	133303	P6.3	500'-1000'		
133419	133444	P6.4	1000'-1500'		
133752	134218	P6.5	1500'-6000'	395	
135154	140457	R7	100'	350	
140724	140745	P7.1	50'-100'		
141048	141140	P7.2	100'-500'		
141301	141353	P7.3	500'-1000'		
141511	141603	P7.4	1000'-1500'		
141937	142538	R8	100'	280	
142856	143852	R9	FL60	275	
145811	150727	R10	FL60	270	
150846	151416	P8.1	FL60-1500'	145	
151534	151608	P8.2	1500'-1000'		
151723	151757	P8.3	1000'-500'		
151903	151947	P8.4	500'-100'		
152106	154514	R11	100'	155	
155347	155426	P9.1	50'-100'		
155525	155600	P9.2	100'-500'		
155703	155735	P9.3	500'-1000'		
155846	155923	P9.4	1000'-1500'		
160049	160621	P9.5	1500'-FL60		
160621	160749	R12	FL60		
161210	172728	R13	100'	180	
172728	172820	P10.1	100'-500'		
173538	173607	P10.2	500'1000'		
173715	173742	P10.3	1000'-1500'		
173917	174417	P10.4	1500'-FL60		

181125

Land at Lyneham

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log ✓ Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log
	✓ Flight Leader pre-flight check form ✓ Flight Leader in-flight check form ✓ Flight Leader in-flight log ✓ Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
	SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEIMOS log Chemistry log
	Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)
	Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track

28/01/97

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To measure the flux of methane, carbon dioxide and nitrous oxide from the UK.

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Weather: Anticyclonic, airflow must be such that air crossing the UK is not contaminated with pollutants from Eastern Europe, *i.e.* airflow ideally from West to East but air flow from North East to South west accepted.

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[2] Execute stepped profile from minimum safe altitude to the top of the boundary layer at 1000feet/min. Profile to be interrupted for short runs approx. 30 seconds) at levels to be decided.

(a) _____, (b) _____, (c) _____, (d) _____, (e) _____

[3] Return to 500 feet for straight and level bag filling run. Remain at this level for 60-70 nm.

[4] Repeat [2] and [3] until between way points V and K.

[5] Cross UK to way point G, continue sampling pattern.

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Intensive sampling periods at 180 kts otherwise 190/5 kts.

SF26: Prof David Fowler(Institute of terrestrail Ecology - Edinburgh) and Dr Geraint Morgan (Open Universtity)

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For your consideration, Leuchars - via south coast - Leuchars takes approx 8hrs (still air) and Leuchars - via north coast - Leuchars takes approx 4hrs (still air). Transit to/from Leuchars will take approx 1hr 45mins.

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	T 8	N5745.0	W00635.0		H
	T 9	N5910.0	W00500.0		I
	T 9A	+N5930.0	W00300.0		I1
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	T11	*N5750.0	W00156.0		K
	T11A	*N5730.0	W00130.0		K1
11	T11B	*N5700.0	W00130.0		K2
10	T11C	N5600.0	E00030.0	BOUNDARY LFA14/LFA12	K3
9	T12	N5500.0	E00130.0	BOUNDARY LFA12/LFA11	L
8	T13	*N5353.0	E00107.0		M
7	T13A	+N5309.0	E00146.0	BOUNDARY LFA11/LFA5	M1
6	T14	*N5230.0	E00220.0	02430.0	N
5	T15	*N5130.0	E00152.0 5110N 0144.0	BOUNDARY LFA5/LFA18	O
4	T16	N5040.0	E00100.0		P
3	T17	*N5000.0	W00032.0	BOUNDARY D059	Q
	T17A	+N5040.0	W00100.0	(ALTERNATE TO T17 - IF REQUIRED)	Q1
	T18	+N5000.0	W00142.2	BOUNDARY D049	R
2	T18A	*N5000.0	W00200.0	BOUNDARY LFA18/LFA2	R1
22	T19	*N5001.0	W00300.0		S
21	T19A	+N4947.0	W00317.0	BOUNDARY D004	S1
20	T20	*N4928.0	W00500.0	BOUNDARY D008A	T
19	T21	N5000.0	W00600.0		U

Leuchars

Edinburgh

Lyneham

Boscombe Down

~~TO HANNAH RICHES 01252 376588~~

~~HANNAH, THIS IS OUR MISSESED FLIGHT PLAN - DO YOU FORSEE ANY PROBLEMS?~~

~~KEN~~

Flight Plan - 28 January 1997

Transit to south coast as convenient, descend to 500 ft (or lower) ASL straight and level. Maintain 500 ft altitude between profile ascents. Transit across Scotland at minimum safe altitude.

A512

GPS data
07:31:53 - 18:16:26

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye

Project: TOWER Date: 28/1/97
Flight No: A512 Page 1 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
11:00:22 TRANSIT		TRANS	6.0K P		190	51.00	-1.86	EGDL T/O 10:42:03 7/8 sc below broken ahead clear over sea and overhead.	
11:07:08		P1	6K P		171	50.51	-1.89	6/8 Broken in below clear above. ^{wides of} Stuckland bay. →	
11:12:00		P1	700 P		192	50.26	-1.99	clear above & below, but cloudy ahead.	
11:13:40		P1.1	500 R		192	50.14	-2.04	interrupt profile at 500' because of cloud ahead	
11:17:49		P1.2	500 R		81	50.01	-2.04	hazy with 2/8 in above	
11:19:04		P1.2	50 R		84	50.02	-1.92		
								Filled bags at 100, 500, 1000, 3000 ft.	
								in cloud layer at 1500 ft.	
11:26:57		R1	700 R		85	50.01	-1.30	Hazy and overcast.	
11:32:42			700 R		88	50.01	-1.00	Hazy and overcast.	
11:34:00								end of run.	
11:39:54		R2	700 R		57	50.02	-50	7/8 in above and hazy - 11:41:20 Bag filling	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye

Project: TIGER Date: 28/1/97
Flight No: A512 Page 2 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
11:57:06		R2	700		58			hazy and cloudy above.	
12:02:11		R2	700	R	49	50.61	0.87	clear above hazy with sc ahead. sea	
12:03:22		R2e	700	R	45	50.65	0.94	Sea surface is clearer.	
12:04:00		R3	700	R	46	50.68	0.97	3 inch mark on video film video of A/E shadow on water.	
12:11:28		R3	700	R	43	50.92	1.36	Sc above, blue sky visible while cliffs of Dover. around. French & UK shores and lots of ship traffic. to Smith's cape	
12:16:16		R3	700	R	37	51.11	1.61	clear above but very hazy... ferry & cat @ 5-7 min	
12:18:20		R3	700	R	36	51.18	1.69	} Hazy some wisps of c below building ahead	
12:18:48		R4	700	R	28	51.20	1.71		clear above. ozone increase at mid then level.
12:21:45								solid cloud below request made to drop below cloud.	
								12:24:09 Dropping below cloud.	
								12:27:01 below cloud at 300. 1042 <u>SS3</u>	
12:32:47						51.79	2.16	climbing to 1200ft to get clear of cloud.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaze.

Project: TIGER Date: 28/1/97
Flight No: A512 Page 3 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12:39:26		R _e	1900	P	26	52.11	2.39	8/8 sc below Hazy ahead - clear overhead.	
12:42:15		P _{4.5}	50	R	22	52.25	2.50	broken cu hazy 1042 <u>SS 2</u> Bag fills @ 100 500 1000 1500 6000ft.	
12:49:48		P _{4.5}	1500	R	327	52.56	2.63	hazy but cloud free above and below.	
12:54:44		R ₅	FL60	P	328	52.76	2.42	Some ci visible ahead but otherwise <u>no cloud</u>	
13:01:55		P ₅	FL60	P	327	53.10	2.00	Oil rig clearly visible - clear.	
13:07:39		R ₆	1000	R	326	53.33	1.73	<u>Haze layer @ 2500 Rad.</u> Good vis. 1036 Regional SSS	
13:21:38		R _{6e}	1000	R	335	53.89	0.99	good vis no cloud but hazy ahead.	
13:29:44		P ₆	50	R	352	54.27	0.89	Some sc ahead but clear cloud free above. 1043 <u>SS 4</u>	
13:42:18		P _{6e}	1000	FL	346	54.47	0.69	100, 500, 1000, 1500 samples. - 3/8 sc below clear above	
13:45:01		P ₇						1500 → soft bag fills and vert structure extra profile. may not be in flight leaders logs.	
13:51:25		P ₇						end of profile.	
13:52:00		R ₇	100	R	345	55.36	0.49	clear 1042 <u>SS 4</u>	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kaye*

Project: *TIGER* Date: *28/1/197*
 Flight No: *A512* Page 4 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
14:02:24		R7	100	R	343	55.93	0.19	clear, some sc on the horizon ahead.	
14:04:59		R7e	100	R	359	55.91	0.16	High level cloud to South and east.	
14:07:54		P7.1	50	R	271	55.90	-0.04	Broken SC ahead Sun shining. 1042 Sea state 4-5	
								100, 500, 1000 & 1500 values.	
								Drop Back to 100 ft	
14:19:37		R8	100	R	275	55.91	-1.09	patches of SC above clear.	
14:25:38		R8c	100	R	277	55.93	-1.57	Clear some patches of SC above and ahead. Run out short to enable 10 mins @ FL60 FL60	
14:28:57		R9	60	FL	270	55.94	-1.87	Clear above and below - hazy overland with some SC patches. Jet contrails available SW Ahead.	
14:38:34		R9e	60	FL	265	55.87	-2.88	good view of Edinburgh.	
14:58:11		R10	60	FL	266	55.67	-5.67	SC below clear above.	
15:07:27		R10	60	FL		55.66	-6.64	sc Below. <u>1040</u>	
15:08:46		P8.1	60	FL	137	55.69	+6.52	SC Below clear above.	
								Copilot time alt 1040 rain water on window Cloud top. 3400 EP 1500 just below cloud.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kaya*

Project: *Tiger*
Flight No: *A512*

Date: *28/7/97*
Page *5* of *6*

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
							<i>1825-1830 on ground</i>		
<i>15:21:06</i>		<i>R11</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>147</i>	<i>55.16</i>	<i>-5.86</i>	<i>a small shower behind us. Cu ahead and patches of Sun.</i> <i>1045 sea state 2</i>	
								<i>Bird strike.</i>	
<i>15:48:51</i>		<i>R11</i>	<i>1000</i>					<i>under sheet of SC but broken cu ahead.</i>	
<i>15:53:48</i>		<i>P9.1</i>	<i>50</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>196</i>	<i>53.64</i>	<i>-5.48</i>	<i>sky ahead and broken cu but SC above</i> <i>visibility good.</i>	
								<i>bag fill runs @ 100 500 1000 1500</i> <i>Broke through cloud top ~ 3700</i>	
<i>16:06:22</i>		<i>P9</i> <i>R12</i>	<i>60</i>	<i>FL</i>	<i>181</i>	<i>52.91</i> <i>52.91</i>	<i>-5.51</i>	<i>sun shining into flight</i> <i>hazy layer of cloud</i> <i>ahead and below</i>	
<i>16:12:10</i>		<i>R13</i>	<i>100ft</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>174</i>	<i>52.57</i>	<i>-5.53</i>	<i>Clear with haze on horizon.</i> <i>1043 SS2.</i>	
<i>16:21:10</i>		<i>R13</i>	<i>100ft</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>178</i>	<i>52.11</i>	<i>-5.52</i>	<i>passed just in front on Stena Ferry Fishguard to Roslar.</i> <i>clear hazy horizon, sun getting low in sky.</i>	
<i>16:26</i>								<i>Sea state 1 1042</i>	
<i>16:33:50</i>								<i>Bright edge of cloud above line to horizon port</i> <i>side clear south cloud north SS.3.</i>	
<i>16:45:24</i>		<i>R13</i>	<i>100ft</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>184</i>			<i>Having passed through the dirtiest Air today</i> <i>continuing 100ft until light fails. Broken cu above</i> <i>hazy horizon. occasional small white cap</i> <i>on sea.</i>	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kenye.

Project: TILER Date: 27/1/97
Flight No: A512 Page 6 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
						16:47:29			
16:57:17		R13	100	R	187	50.25	-5.90	Light fading but horizon good broken in overhead lands end lighthouse	
17:05:37		R13	100	R	127	49.94	-5.73	visible 1/2 in still good (1041 SS 4) light	
17:11:40		R13	100	R	123	49.77	-5.41	sea state 5	
17:18:07		R13	100	R	85	49.65	-5.04	in clean air Sc above.	
17:25:31		R13	100	R	87	49.66	-4.54	Sc above horizon still good.	
17:27:32		R13 P10.1	100	R	88	49.66	-4.37	staying visual @ 550 ft. SC ABOVE and sea below. getting dark.	
								1000 2000 and 1000 or 1500 samples plus 6000 out of the boundary layer.	
17:44:17		P10 and F160		P	19	49.93	-3.35	completely dark no obs possible. out on clouds 3000.	
17:46:17		last bag filled.						END END OF SCIENCE ALL BAGS FILLED!	

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A512 Date: 28/1/96 User: A. KATE
Interactive by: I. RUE
Date: 30/1/97

Renav

KALMAN FILTERING APPLIED

TWC

Profile plotted: NO — NO DEEP PROFILES CARRIED OUT IN FLIGHT
Line chosen: Profile / Whole flight / Other

a = -0.5499 E+1
b = +0.3083 E-2
c = +0.5241 E-6

LWC

OK

Heimann / Barnes

NOT USED

ICTP — RECALIBRATED

FWK — NOT CONNECTED DUE TO LACK OF REQUIRED QUALITY DATA

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: 4512

Date: 28/1/97

A/S Name: A. KAYE

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for 3, OPEN UN1, J.E. LRF
2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period
3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project
4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long? 10 yrs
5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO GAVE TAPE TO A. KAYE
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?
6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in?
7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: AS12 Date: 28/1/17

Page...of 2

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
<u>0756</u>	REF +	5	<u>0566</u>	✓			
	REF -	7	<u>2754</u>	✓			Approx 0568
	AOSS	19	<u>4095</u>		F/S TORQUE		Approx 2858
	AOA	18	<u>6095</u>		O/S 4.5 F/S TORQUE		2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	<u>0000</u>		O/S 3.5		2047 st. and level
	PR HT	8	<u>3460</u>	<u>280</u>	✓		As Indicated 0000
	CABP	14	<u>3302</u>	<u>1020</u>	✓		As Altimeter
	A/S	9	<u>0000</u>				As ASI 0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	<u>0161</u>				
	UP2S	82	<u>0150</u>				
	UIRS	83	<u>2018</u>				
	UP1Z	84	<u>0150</u>	✓			Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	<u>0144</u>	✓			Approx 0149
	UIRZ	86	<u>2032</u>	✓			Approx 2061
	UP1T	87	<u>2777</u>				As IAT
	UP2T	88	<u>2874</u>				As IAT
	UIRT	89	<u>2831</u>				As IAT
	LP1S	91	<u>0102</u>				
	LP2S	92	<u>4095</u>				
	LIRS	93	<u>4095</u>				
	LP1Z	94	<u>4095</u>				
	LP2Z	95	<u>4095</u>				Approx 0150
	LIRZ	96	<u>4095</u>				Approx 0146
	LP1T	97	<u>4095</u>				Approx 2050
	LP2T	98	<u>4095</u>				As IAT
	LIRT	99	<u>4095</u>				As IAT
	J/W	42	<u>0997</u>	✓			As IAT
	NEPE	47			<u>0.0</u>		As Indicated 0000
	HYGR	58	<u>2472</u>	<u>0</u>			
	HYCC	59	<u>0693</u>	✓			696-901
	FDEW	138	<u>1992</u>	<u>0</u>			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	FSTA	139	<u>0667</u>				
	DTF	10	<u>0925</u>	<u>2</u>			
	DTC	11	<u>5</u>				
	NDTF	23	<u>2572</u>	<u>2</u>			
	NDTC	24	<u>5</u>				same as De-Iced
	INCT	48	<u>2671</u>	✓			
	CCN	140					
	TWCD	70	<u>283</u>				less than 4095 if ON
	TSAM	72	<u>0240</u>				0000-4094
	O3	100	<u>3488</u>				0640-1860 < min
	O3P	108	<u>2804</u>				
	O3RG	113	<u>0692</u>				$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$

ALTIMETER
(P/R)

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	0512	✓		Flight No.
	GMTM	2	Hex	0780	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0750	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	INCH	49	Dec	11	✓		Event Mark Counter
	LATC	160	Dec	0000			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	0000			Longitude
		1502		2445			
		2445		1024			
		3754		2124			
		2445		3744			
		2445		2945			
				0127			Multiplx'd Hkeeping

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height:

GMT	PARA.	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES
	TWCD	70	✓	2164		0001-4095
	TNOS	71	✓	0821		2000-3460 > min
	TSAM	72	✓	0048		0840-1860 > min
	TAMB	73	?	2123	100	2400-3200
	TSRC	74	✓	2219		2160-2470
	HTR1	75	✓	2280		0000-4095 > 4095
	HTR2	76	✓	2145		0000-4095 > 4095
	ISRC	77	✓	1022		0001-1230 > min
	STAT	78	✓	4272		4095
	EV1V	170		2045		
	EV2V	171		2045		
	NPWR	172		3555		
	EVIC	173		3267		
	EV2C	174		2167		

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-flight only)

PARA NO	POSITION	DOVE	COVERS	OBSCURERS
81,84,87	Port	Clear	Large/Small	
82,85,88	Stbd	Red	Large/Small	
83,86,89	Centre	Silicon	Large/Small	
91,94,97	Port	Clear	Large/Small	
92,95,98	Stbd	Red	Large/Small	
93,96,99	Centre	Silicon	Large/Small	

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: AS12 Date: 28/1/97

Page...of 2

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1103	REF +	5	0567	✓			
	REF -	7	2853	✓			Approx 0568
	AOSS	19	1882	✓	F/S TORQUE		Approx 2858
	AOA	18	1875	✓	O/S TORQUE		2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	4095	✓	>5000		2047 st. and level
	PR HT	8	3123		0000		As Indicated 0000
	CABP	14	3395		0000		As Altimeter
	A/S	9	2169		1031	1030	
1225	UP1S	81	0906		280		As ASI 0000 - 0100
	UP2S	82	0857				
	UIRS	83	1868				
	UP1Z	84	0151	✓			Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	0147	✓			Approx 0149
	UIRZ	86	2041	✓			Approx 2061
	UP1T	87	2705				As IAT
	UP2T	88	2716				As IAT
	UIRT	89	2740				As IAT
	LP1S	91	0324				
	LP2S	92	0218				
	LIRS	93	1973				
	LP1Z	94	0148	✓			Approx 0150
	LP2Z	95	0102	✓			Approx 0146
	LIRZ	96	2057	✓			Approx 2050
	LP1T	97	2082				As IAT
	LP2T	98	2702				As IAT
	LIRT	99	2701				As IAT
1549	J/W	42	1400		M.Z.		As IAT
	NEPH	47					As Indicated 0000
	HYGR	58	2502		1		
	HYCC	59	0700	✓			696-901
	FDEW	138	1999				DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	FSTA	139	0608		0		
	DTF	10	2875		9		
	DTC	11	5				
	NDTF	23	2515		9		
	NDTC	24	5				same as De-Iced
	INCT	48	2606				
	CCN	140					
	TWCD	70	2218				less than 4095 if ON
	TSAM	72	1524				0000-4094
	O3	100	0141				0640-1860 < min
	O3P	106	2080				
	O3RG	113	1708				$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1020	FL NO	1	Hex	512			Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0702			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0722			Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0331			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
3171	1508	3172	0702	3172	3719	3171	0158
	2855						
	LATC	160	Dec	0502	52N		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4033	5W		Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: 100

GMT	PARA.	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70	2256			0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2518			2000-3480	< min
	TSAM	72	1278			0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2725			2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2241			2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	1240			0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	1520			0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1074			0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095	✓		4095	
	EV1V	170	3473				
	EV2V	171	3138				
	NPWR	172	2683				
	EVIC	173	4079				
	EV2C	174	4004				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 512.....

Date28/1/17.....

Page1..... of4.....

Video Tape	
No. A512 #1	
Ends 1356	
☒ FFC / ☐ DFC / ☐ RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	51° 30.41'N	51° 30.41'N
Long	001° 59.16'W	001° 59.17'W
Time	0813	0814
Status	5s OK	GC AUGIV

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ y / ☐ n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ y / ☐ n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	☐ y / ☐ n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr		Wind/Sea st.
072421		DATA ON								
084400		SIT INU TO NAV								
09403		T/O RAF LINDSEY								
095623		START VIDEO A512#1 COUNT = 0000								
10708	29	6000		180	100	0.5	-17	OFF		
111344	30	500'	104	200						
11749	31	500'		085		4.9	2.4	OFF		
11904	32	50'	102							S=5
12004	34	100'								
2038	36	500'								
2142	38	500'								
2211	39	1000'								
12329	42	1000'								
12551	44	1500'								

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A S12.....

Date 28/1/97.....

Page 2 of 4.....

Video Tape	
No. <u>A512#2</u>	
Ends <u>1356</u>	
☒ FFC / ☐ DFC / ☐ RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	<u>52 49.45N</u>	<u>52 51.45N</u>
Long	<u>002 20.65E</u>	<u>002 17.58E</u>
Time	<u>1256</u>	<u>1257</u>
Status	<u>5's</u>	<u>NAV</u>

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ y / ☐ n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ y / ☐ n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	☒ y / ☐ n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
				<u>START P 4.2</u>	<u>4.2</u>				
<u>24400</u>	<u>126</u>	<u>100'</u>		<u>020</u>					
				<u>END P 4.2</u>					
<u>24431</u>	<u>128</u>	<u>500'</u>							
				<u>START P 4.3</u>					
<u>24551</u>	<u>131</u>	<u>500'</u>							
				<u>END P 4.3</u>					
<u>24625</u>	<u>132</u>	<u>1000'</u>							
				<u>START P 4.4</u>					
<u>24729</u>	<u>135</u>	<u>1000'</u>							
				<u>END P 4.4</u>					
<u>24803</u>	<u>136</u>	<u>1500'</u>							
				<u>START P 4.5</u>					
<u>24948</u>	<u>139</u>	<u>1500'</u>							
				<u>END P 4.5</u>		<u>START RUN 5</u>			
<u>25442</u>	<u>141</u>	<u>FL6000'</u>	<u>1013</u>	<u>330</u>	<u>190</u>	<u>L3</u>	<u>-12</u>	<u>OFF</u>	
				<u>END RUN 5</u>		<u>START P 5</u>			
<u>25155</u>	<u>147</u>	<u>FL60</u>	<u>1013</u>	<u>330</u>	<u>190</u>				
				<u>END P 5</u>		<u>START RUN 6</u>			
<u>25729</u>	<u>148</u>	<u>1000'</u>	<u>1036</u>	<u>330</u>	<u>195</u>	<u>5</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>OFF</u>	<u>360/16</u> <u>SS=3</u>
				<u>END RUN 6</u>					
<u>27138</u>	<u>164</u>	<u>1000'</u>	<u>1036</u>	<u>330</u>	<u>198</u>	<u>5</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>OFF</u>	
				<u>START PROFILE P 6.17</u>					
<u>2942</u>	<u>170</u>	<u>500'</u>	<u>1042</u>	<u>355</u>	<u>170</u>				<u>SS=4</u>
				<u>END P 6.1</u>					
<u>29004</u>	<u>172</u>	<u>100'</u>							

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 512.....

Date 28/1/97.....

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Video Tape	
No.	AS12 #2
Ends	1654
☒ FFC / ☐ DFC / ☐ RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	55 54.07N	55 52.60N
Long	007 46.47W	007 57.57W
Time	1429	1430
Status	53	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ y / ☐ n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ y / ☐ n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	☒ y / ☐ n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
		500'		END P 7.2					
41140	220	500'		P					
				START P 7.3					
41307	223	500'							
				END P 7.3					
141353	225	1000'		START P 7.4					
41571	227	1000'							
				END P 7.4					
41603	228	1500'		START P 7.5					
		1000'		START RUN 8					
41957	231	100'	1042	280	190	7	4	OFF	SS=4
				END RUN 8					
42535	240	100'	1042	280	190	7.2	3.4	OFF	
	↑			START RUN 9					
42856	241	FL60		275	185	3	-4	OFF	
				END RUN 9					
43832	251	FL60		270	182	3.9	-4.1	OFF	
				START RUN 10					
45811	252	FL60	1042	270		3.9	-5	OFF	
				END RUN 10					
50727	261	FL60							

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 512.....

Date 28/1/97.....

Page 4.... of 4.....

Video Tape	
No. <u>AS12#2</u>	
Ends <u>1654</u>	
<u>(FFC)</u> / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	<u>51 52.6 N</u>	<u>51 50.00 N</u>
Long	<u>005 30.8 W</u>	<u>005 31.7 W</u>
Time	<u>1025</u>	<u>1026</u>
Status	<u>S's</u>	<u>NAV</u>

DRS recording to HORACE	<u>(y)</u> / n
HORACE recording to disc	<u>(y)</u> / n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	<u>(y)</u> / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
				<u>START</u>	<u>P</u>	<u>9.4</u>			
<u>55746</u>	<u>310</u>	<u>1000'</u>							
				<u>END</u>	<u>P</u>	<u>9.4</u>			
<u>55923</u>	<u>311</u>	<u>1500'</u>							
				<u>START</u>	<u>P</u>	<u>9.5</u>			
<u>60049</u>	<u>314</u>	<u>1500'</u>							
				<u>END</u>	<u>P</u>	<u>9.5</u>	<u>START</u>	<u>RUN</u>	<u>12</u>
<u>1600621</u>	<u>315</u>	<u>FL6000</u>	<u>1023</u>	<u>185</u>	<u>195</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>-6</u>	<u>OFF</u>	
				<u>END</u>	<u>RUN</u>	<u>12</u>			
<u>60749</u>	<u>318</u>	<u>FL60</u>	<u>1073</u>	<u>190</u>	<u>185</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>-6</u>	<u>OFF</u>	
				<u>START</u>	<u>RUN</u>	<u>13</u>			
<u>61210</u>	<u>319</u>	<u>100'</u>	<u>1043</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>190</u>	<u>7</u>	<u>4</u>	<u>OFF</u>	<u>SS=2</u>
				START	RUN	13			
			1043						<u>SS=13</u>
<u>64935</u>	<u>383</u>	<u>END</u>	<u>VIDEO</u>	<u>TAPE</u>	<u>A512#2</u>	<u>CARD</u>	<u>=</u>	<u>9977</u>	
<u>65019</u>	<u>380</u>	<u>START</u>	<u>VIDEO</u>	<u>TAPE</u>	<u>A512#3</u>	<u>CARD</u>	<u>=</u>	<u>0000</u>	
<u>1705</u>			<u>1041</u>						<u>SS=4</u>
<u>1711</u>									<u>SS=5</u>
<u>1719</u>									<u>075/20kt</u>
				<u>END</u>	<u>RUN</u>	<u>13</u>	<u>START</u>	<u>P</u>	<u>10.1</u>
<u>72728</u>	<u>426</u>	<u>100'</u>							
				<u>END</u>	<u>P</u>	<u>10.1</u>			
<u>72820</u>	<u>427</u>	<u>500'</u>							
				<u>START</u>	<u>P</u>	<u>10.2</u>			
<u>173538</u>	<u>425</u>	<u>500'</u>							

Video Tape	
No.	AS12#1
Ends	1356
FFC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	50 00.16N	49 59.75N
Long	007 12.85W	007 08.66W
Time	1129	1150
Status	5's	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ / n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ / n
SATCOM sending pos reports	☒ / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			START P 2.0			3.1			
2527	46	1500'							
			END P 3.1						
2633	45	700'							
			START RUN 1						
2657	50	700'	090	180	4.1	3.0	OFF		
			END RUN 1						
3535	60	700'	090	188	4.2	2.0			
			START RUN 2						
3954	63	700'	090	190	4.2	1.9	OFF		
			058						
			END RUN 2						
0322	85	700'	059	200	4.4	1.8	OFF		
			START RUN 3						
0400	86	700'	050	180	4.8	-0.2	OFF		
			END RUN 3						
1720	104	700'	040	192	4.9	0.9	OFF		
			START RUN 4						
1843	106	700	1042	030	192	4.7	1.5	OFF	
			END RUN 4						
3932	120	2000↓	1042	030	190				SS=3
			START P 4.1						
4215	121	50'							
			END P 4.1						
4258	122	100'	1042						SS=2

Video Tape	
No.	AS12#2
Ends	1654
☒ FFC / ☐ DFC / ☐ RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	55 39.35N	55 41.25N
Long	000 20.55E	000 18.15E
Time	1400	1401
Status	S3	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ / ☐ n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ / ☐ n
SATCOM sending pos reports	☒ / ☐ n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			START P6.2						
133118	174	100'							
			END P6.2						
133148	176	500'							
			START P6.3						
133242	178	500'							
			END P6.3						
33303	179 179	1000'							
			START P6.4						
33419	182	1000'							
			END P6.4						
33444	183	1500'							
			START P6.5						
13752	186	1500'							
			END P6.5						
34218	187	6000'	1042	395					
			START RUN 7						
55154	198	100'	1042	350	190	7.5	4.1	OFF	SS=3/4
55335	201		END VIDEO A 512#1			COUNT = 6043			
55428	203		START VIDEO AS12#2			COUNT = 0000			
55520			HANNAN CAL Prog 6			10 → 0			
			END RUN 7						
40457	211	100'	1042	350	110				
			START P 7.1						
40724	213 213	50'	1042						SS=4/5
			END P 7.1						
40745	215	100'							
			START P 7.2						
41048	219	100'							

Video Tape
 No. AS12#2
 Ends 1654
 (FFC) / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	54 26.77N	54 24.16N
Long	005 08.71W	005 09.95W
Time	1537	1537
Status	5's	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE (y)/n
 HORACE recording to disc (y)/n
 SATCOM sending pos reports (y)/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/Sea st.
				START PROFILE		8.1			
150846	262	FLOOR		145	180				
				END PROFILE		8.1			
151416	263	1500'		165					
				START PROFILE		8.2			
151534	266	1500'							
				END P8.2					
151608	268	1000'							
				START P8.3					
151723	271	1000'							
				END P8.3					
151757	272	500'							
				START P8.4					
151903	275	500'							
				END P8.4					
151947	276	100'							
				START P8.5 RUN 11					
152106	279	100'	1045	155	180	8	4	OFF	SS=2
				START P8.5					
				END RUN 11					
154514	296	100'							SS=1
				START P 9.1					
155347	299	50'	1045						SS=2
				END P9.1					
155426	300	100'							
				START P 9.2					
155525	302	100'							
				END P9.2					
155600	304	500'							
				START P 9.3					
155703	306	500'							
				END P9.3					
155735	307	1000'							

Video Tape
 No. A512#3
 Ends 1950
 (FFC) / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	50 11.18N	50 14.05N
Long	003 10.25W	003 08.17W
Time	1750	1750
Status	5s	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE (y) / n
 HORACE recording to disc (y) / n
 SATCOM sending pos reports (y) / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			END P 10.2						
173607	437	1000'							
			START P 10.3						
73715	439	1000'							
			END P 10.3						
73742	440	1500'							
			START P 10.4						
73917	443	1500'							
			END P 10.4						
74417	445	FL000							
			TRANSIT FOR LYNEHAM						
81125			LAND LYNEHAM						
181340	447		A512#3	VIDEO OFF	COUNT = 3571				
81550			DATA OFF						
					GPS POS ON PAN AT LYNEHAM				
					51° 30.36			NORTH	
					0010 59.15			WEST	

- ① LOSS TORQUE A-D - HIGH @ 4:5
- ② USUAL LOWER SIDE PROGRAM PILE-FLIGHT / AND AFTER T/O
- ③ HORACE CALCULATED WINDS / WIND SPEED QUITE W/OUT COMPARED TO NAVS WINDS - INU SEEMS OK, VANDS SEEM OK. OTHER STANDARDS PARAS SEEM OK
- ④ PRE-FLIGHTING DATA NEEDS TO BE RECHECKED WITH TY-LMAPS.

GET 4 POSITIONS FOR THE VAN DOORS - DO NOT SCAN

From: XV208 28/01/97 1234Z
 To: Aircraft Manager
 Hi

We are having some problems with cloud. Can you check the latest satpic and let us know the location of low cloud in the north sea.

Cheers

Ian

$\underline{1200 \text{ Vis}}$ All low level (^{mostly} Sc)
 cloud
 up to $52\frac{1}{2}^{\circ}N$, $E \rightarrow W$. Thin cloud
 Then virtually clear slot ~~with~~
 near E coast up to $57^{\circ}N$, $2\frac{1}{2}^{\circ}W$
~~to~~
 Broken cloud on W. Scottish coast
 $56^{\circ}N \rightarrow 54^{\circ}N$, $5-6^{\circ}W$
 Mostly clear Irish Sea
 $\downarrow$ $52^{\circ}N \rightarrow 5^{\circ}W$ then
 cloud.
 Cloud SW peninsula.
 until approx Plymouth
 then mostly cloud free $\rightarrow$ IOW.

Flight Plan - 28 January 1997

Transit to south coast as convenient, descend to 500 ft (or lower) ASL straight and level. Maintain 500 ft altitude between profile ascents. Transit across Scotland at minimum safe altitude.

P denotes profile ascent/descent to clear of boundary layer

○ = approximate start position of PSAP filter exposure.

P.S.A.P Log

Flight No. A512.....

Date 28.1.97.....

Project ROADS BRITAIN.....

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ Start of Run	Height	Run	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ End of Run	Remarks
Set to DRS 0317 time ✓	New filter Tr = 1.000	Set to 2.5 lpm	21.7	Levels 35 156.	Ave = 30 s	Handwritten FILTER	← Preflight ONLY
105420	0.847	2.45	0.8	FL60		(1)	Switch on, same filter in (P1)
111039	0.847	2.4	2.1	FL30	P1 ↓	(1)	On profile down.
1118							End Profile, change filter (P2)
112443	0.995	2.62	2.2	1500ft	P2.	(2)	First stepped profile up.
113105	0.990	2.45	3.0	1000ft	R1	(2)	In Run 1
113536	0.987	2.45	1.6	1000ft	R2	(2)	Start Run 2
113954	0.986	2.46	1.2	700ft	R3	(2)	End Run 2 / Start R3
115210	0.981	2.45	2.7	700ft	R2	(2)	
120304	0.974	2.44	1.5	700ft	R3	(2)	End Run 2 / Start Run 3
121740	0.970	2.44	0.7	700ft	R3	(2)	Near end of Run 3
122413	0.968	2.43	1.6	descending	R4	(2)	Descend to try + clear cloud. - too low to track
123232	0.965	2.50	1.6	climbing thru 1000ft	R4	(2)	Level at 1200ft to avoid cloud.

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	$B_a \times 10^6$ Start of Run	Height	Run	$B_a \times 10^6$ End of Run	Remarks
123950	0.964	2.5	0.1	700ft	4	FILTER (2)	End Run 4.
124305	0.961	2.57	5.8	100ft	P4.1 ^r	(2)	More soot at this level.
124522	0.958	2.54	7.2	500ft	P4.2	(2)	High level
124705	0.956	2.50	0.5	1000ft	P4.3	(2)	Soot dropped off at this height
124835	0.956	2.45	0.0	1500ft	P4.4	(2)	Back to clean air
125440	0.957	2.48	0.0	6000ft	R5	(2)/(3)	Change filter, / start Run
130136	1.000	2.47	0.0	6000ft	R5	(3)/(4)	End Run / change filter
130738	0.992	2.96	1.5	1000ft	R6	(4)	start , start Run 6
132156	0.989	2.53	0.8	1000ft	R6	(4)	End Run
132911	0.988	2.56	1.8	300ft		(4)	Descending
133004	0.988	2.52	3.5	100ft	R6 P6.1	(4)	In the run N. of Humber est.
133206	0.987	2.49	0.9	500ft	P6.2	(4)	Lower soot amounts than previous
133335	0.986	2.45	0.8	1000ft	P6.3	(4)	profiles
133409	0.986	2.45	1.6	1000ft	R6	(4)	
133540	0.985	2.42	0.7	1500ft	P6.4	(4)	
133805	0.985	2.40	0.3	1500ft ↗	P6.5	(4)	Climb up to 6000ft.
134835	0.985	2.55	0.1	1000ft	R6	(4)	Profile down
135005	0.984	2.56	1.9	500ft	P	(4)	
135220	0.983	2.51	91.7	100ft	R7	(4)	Not Not as much as S. Coast.

P.S.A.P Log

Flight No. ...A512.....

Date28-1-97.....

Project ...ROUND BRITAIN.....

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ Start of Run	Height	Run	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ End of Run	Remarks
Set to DRS time	New filter Tr = 1.000	Set to 2.5 lpm		Levels 1	Ave = s	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ FILTER	← Preflight ONLY
140302	0.977	2.52	1.1	100ft	R7	(4)	Fairly low counts.
140805	0.976	2.51	1.4	100ft	P7.1	(4) (4)	Counts again lower than before
141105	0.975	2.49	2.2	500ft	P7.2	(4)	Hdy twds Abbr head.
141435	0.973	2.46	0.2	1000'	P7.3	(4)	Above inversion
141745	0.974	2.41	0.1	1500'	P7.4	(4)	Clean.
142035	0.970	2.50	10.5	100'	R8	(4)	Counts comparable w/ S. coast 1/1s
142340	0.964	2.50	7.2	100'	R8	(4)	Last run on E-coast
142540	0.961	2.51	7.0	100'	R8	(4)	End Run, climb to FL60
143030	1.00	1.53	0.0	FL60	R9	(5)	Change filter. Over land run
143836	0.999	2.52	0.0	FL60	R9	(5)	End Run.
145835	0.999	2.4	0.7	FL60	R10	(5)	Slow down, crossing W. coast.
150715	1.000	2.50	0.0	FL60	R10	(5) / (6)	End run, change filter

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ Start of Run	^{40/56} Height	Run	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ End of Run	Remarks
151105	1.000	2.56	0.00	FL60	P8.1x	End of Run FILTER (6)	Ready for Profile down
151240	0.999	2.49	7.0	3000ft	P8.1	(6)	Starting to see some particles
151508	0.999	2.48	0.0	1500ft		(6)	Clean!
151640	0.999	2.51	1.0	1000ft	P8.2	(6)	"
151835	0.998	2.56	1.0	500ft	P8.3	(6)	"
152020	0.998	2.58	0.4	100ft	P8.4	(6)	"
153618	0.998	2.52	0.0	100ft	R11	(6)	
154518	0.995	2.50	1.7	100ft	R11	(6)	End Run.
155256	0.989	2.51	0.0	300ft	—	(6)/(7)	Change filter
155530	1.000	2.45	0.2	500ft	P9.2	(7)	Clean
155633	0.999 1.000	2.42	0.0	500ft	P9.3	(7)	"
155805	0.999	2.45	0.6	1000ft	P9.3	(7)	"
160020	0.999	2.43	0.0	1500ft	P9.4	(7)	"
161235	0.997	2.47	4.3	100ft	R13	(7)	Back into the polluted air now.
162045	0.983	2.47	4.5	100ft	R13	(7)	Abeam S. Wales
162639	0.973	2.47	10.1	100ft	R13	(7)	Getting much longer land crossings
163333	0.953	2.46	8.7	100ft	R13	(7)	Counts falling back now.
164305	0.934	2.47	10.8	100ft	R13	(7)	
164728	0.924	2.45	15.8	100ft	R13	(7)	

P.S.A.P Log

Flight No. A512

Date 28.1.97

Project ROUND BRITAIN

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ Start of Run	Height	Run	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ End of Run	Remarks
Set to DRS time	New filter Tr = 1.000	Set to 2.5 lpm		Levels 1	Ave = s		← Preflight ONLY
165116	0.913	2.45	12.2	100ft	R13	⑦ / ⑧	change filter before lands End
165433	0.999	2.46	9.0	100ft	R13	⑧	/ back into clear air
16 170108	0.992	2.54	2.0	100ft	R13	⑧	almost at lands End. 2 min
170540	0.990	2.54	1.5	100ft	R13	⑧	running along south coast.
171251	0.988	2.49	1.4	100ft	R13	⑧	
172145	0.982	2.50	3.0	100ft	R13	⑧	beyond the Lizard, still fairly clear
172737	0.976	2.51	3.6	100ft	R13	⑧	End Run
172905	0.976	2.48	2.0	550'	R13 P10.1	⑧	stopped profile, getting dark
173311	0.974	2.47	1.9	550'	P10.	⑧	stay at 101 till past dog over.
173633	0.972	2.49	1.1	1000ft	P10.2	⑧	Clear.
173835	0.971	2.47	1.6	1500'	P10.3	⑧	clear.
174422	0.972	2.34	2.3	FL60	P10.4	⑧ / ⑨	climb to FL60, change filter.

A512 28-JAN-97 16:31:45 349 Ω 51.56 -5.61 RV P/

HDG deg 185.	SPR mb 1037.	PHGT kft -0.6	TAS knts 168.	TAT C 7.1	DEW C 4.6	WIND deg 032/11
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OZONE MR 18.17 PSAP LIN 1.45
ppb E-5m-1

2.50
2.00
1.50
1.00
0.50
0.00

A B C D E F G H
SELECT PARAS FREQ ZOOM VIDEO HELP

A512 28-JAN-97 17:46:15 446 Ω 50.02 -3.35 RV P/

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
16.	812.	6.0	199.	1.1	-10.5	128/12

OZONE MR 47.60 PSAP LIN 5.00
ppb E-5m-1

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

50.00
37.50
25.00
12.50
0.00

A512 28-JAN-97 17:44:36 445 49.94 -3.35 AS P

HDS deg	SPR m/s	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
10.	811.	6.0	171.	0.5	-10.5	129/12

600 -30 -20 -10 0 GE IP

700 TWC IP

10

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A512 28-JAN-97 17:04:30 412 Ω 49.98 -5.81 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
125.	1035.	-0.6	159.	7.6	2.2	337/5

OZONE MR 41.01 PSAP LIN 0.12
ppb E-5m-1

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A512 28-JAN-97 15:58:12 308 Q 53.37 -5.51 RV / F

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT k ft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
177.	1005.	0.2	158.	5.7	2.5	002/14

OZONE MR 38.51 PSAP LIN 0.05
ppb E-5m-1

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A512 28-JAN-97 15:32:09 288 Ω 54.72 -5.39 RV P

HDG deg 148.	SPR mb 1038.	PHGT kft -0.7	TAS knots 163.	TAT C 8.0	DEW C 4.3	WIND deg m/s 324/14
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OZONE MR 40.25 PSAP LIN 0.00
ppb E-5m-1

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A512 28-JAN-97 15:25:03 281 -- 55.02 -5.71 AS P1

HQC	SEP	PHST	TAT	DEM	WIND
148.	1038.	158.	7.6	5.0	317/11
deg	ms	krms	C	SEC	mps

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A512 28-JAN-97 14:01:48 209 Ω 55.75 0.23 RV P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
340.	1036.	-0.6	168.	7.4	4.7	222 / 4

OZONE MR 34.73 PSEP LIN 0.22
ppb E-5m-1

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A512 28-JAN-97 13:56:03 206 Ω 55.48 0.42 RV P

HDG deg 339.	SPR mb 1037.	PHGT kft -0.6	TAS knots 173.	TAT C 7.4	DEW C 4.6	WIND deg m/s 209/3
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OZONE MR 34.41 PSAP LIN 0.24
ppb E-5m-1

0.50
0.50
0.25
0.25
0.15
0.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A512 28-JAN-97 13:36:27 185 Ω 54.57 0.82 RV P

HDG deg 345.	SPR mb 987.	PHGT kft 0.7	TAS knots 164.	TAT C 4.8	DEW C 2.8	WIND deg m/s 092 / 4
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OZONE MR 40.47 233P LIN 0.05
PCC E-5M-1

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM	EXIT	FILE	VIDEO	HELP

A512 28-JAN-97 12:56:57 143 -- 52.86 2.31 AS P

MODE	EFF	PHST	TRE	TAT	DEW	WIND
deg	TC	km	km/s	C	C	deg m/s
326.	812.	6.0	196.	-3.2	-10.8	101/8

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A512 28-JAN-97 12:47:09 133 Ω 52.44 2.61 RV F

HDG deg 17.	SPR mb 1004.	PHGT kft 0.3	TAS knots 163.	TAT C 5.1	DEW C 1.6	WIND deg m/s 186/5
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OZONE MR 39.12 PSAP LIN 0.04
ppb E-5m-1

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	

A512 28-JAN-97 12:10:09 093 Ω 50.87 1.28 RV

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
43.	1013.	0.0	176.	4.6	0.4	128 / 3

OZONE MR 35.75 PSEP LIN 0.07
 P26 E-5m-1
 100.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
ELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VTFNO		HCI D

A512 28-JAN-97 11:55:57 079 Ω 50.43 0.47 RV P

HDG deg T 58.	SPR mb 1014.	PHGT kft 0.0	TAS knots 171.	TAT C 3.9	DEW C 2.9	WIND deg 311 / 2
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OZONE MR 29.13 PSAP LIN 0.32
ppb E-5m-1

1.25
1.00
0.75
0.50
0.25
0.00

A B C D E F G H
SELECT PARAS FREQ ZOOM VIDEO HELP

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:20m

Prepared and drawn in the Geographic Institute, Helsinki, Finland (Material from Rijks) Amended July 1996

SCALE OF NAUTICAL MILES
100 200 300 400 500 600 700

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR 4 MB INTERVALS
80 25 10
80 40 25 15 10

ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 1200 UTC 28 JAN 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:20m

FSXX EGRR 24H MSLP FORECAST VT 0000 UTC 29 JAN 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection. Standard Parallel 60°N. Original scale 1:20m

Prepared and drawn in the Cartographic Section, MET.O.164., Anstrutell. Miss.D.J.Cornwall D.O. from 15/1/69. Amended July '99d

PAGE.001

MET OFFICE ** TOTAL PAGE.001 **

28 JAN '97 04:52

**CAMBORNE
03608
AT 11Z**

10	330	19
15	020	9
20	110	29
25	085	49
30	080	37
40	080	37
50	075	32
60	065	26
70	035	25
85	025	13
100		
MAX	10897	
	095	61
TROP	185	-66
	070	23
10	1620	
15	1364	
20	1186	
25	1048	
30	932	
40	738	
50	577	
70	319	
85	164	
100	34	
10	256.0	
15	178.0	
20	138.0	
25	116.0	
30	194.0	
40	161.0	
50	258.2	
60	285.3	
70	130.9	
85	543.5	
100		
10	-58	
15	-58	
20	-63	

**HERSTMONCEUX
03882
AT 11Z**

10	355	6
15	025	20
20	090	38
25	075	69
30	070	46
40	065	46
50	055	46
60	060	43
70	043	28
85	065	22
100		
MAX	10843	
	080	74
TROP	222	-63
	075	70
10	1619	
15	1385	
20	1185	
25	1048	
30	929	
40	738	
50	575	
70	317	
85	163	
100	35	
10	256.0	
15	178.0	
20	139.0	
25	117.0	
30	196.0	
40	160.0	
50	258.2	
60	283.5	
70	129.8	
85	541.7	
100		
10	-58	
15	-58	
20	-61	

**HEMSBY
03496
AT 11Z**

10	345	15
15	030	15
20		
25	075	48
30	070	43
40	060	30
50	060	30
60	035	31
70	035	31
85	020	17
100	015	12
100		
MAX	NIL	
TROP	199	-68
	075	43
10	1619	
15	1361	
20	1185	
25	1049	
30	932	
40	737	
50	576	
70	318	
85	164	
100	34	
10	256.0	
15	176.0	
20	136.0	
25	117.0	
30	195.0	
40	161.0	
50	258.2	
60	284.2	
70	130.3	
85	542.5	
100		
10	-59	
15	-60	
20	-68	

**ABERPORTH
03502
AT 11Z**

10	325	13
15	360	11
20	095	45
25	100	40
30	090	22
40	060	19
50	075	20
60	085	21
70	035	17
85	020	14
100	080	9
100		
MAX	NIL	
TROP	208	-67
	095	42
10	1619	
15	1364	
20	1189	
25	1052	
30	935	
40	740	
50	580	
70	320	
85	165	
100	35	
10	255.0	
15	175.0	
20	137.0	
25	117.0	
30	195.0	
40	160.0	
50	259.7	
60	285.6	
70	130.4	
85	543.5	
100		
10	-59	
15	-60	
20	-66	

FACIT 4-UP
28 JAN '97 13:46

12Z 28 JAN 1997

10	300	10	335	10
15	280	17	030	21
20	270	50	075	17
25	275	59	055	76
30	285	48	065	66
40	300	47	060	60
50	300	33	055	39
60	380	24	030	29
70			060	17
85			050	16
100				
MAX	MIL			
TROPO	191 -72		18115	70
10	270	30	185	-65
15			070	35
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**STORNOWAY
03026
AT 11Z**

10	255	16
15	255	28
20	240	36
25	255	36
30	250	36
40	255	28
50	260	31
60	265	30
70	275	24
85	270	10
100		
MAX	MIL	
TROP	196	-71
	240	37
10	1612	
15	1359	
20	1186	
25	1049	
30	932	
40	738	
50	577	
70	320	
85	165	
100	34	
10	293.0	
15	173.0	
20	137.0	
25	117.0	
30	104.0	
40	161.0	
50	257.5	
70	285.5	
85	130.7	
100	543.0	
10	-76	
15	-61	
20	-69	

**VALENTIA
03953**

10	505	12
15	325	6
20	160	33
25	120	37
30	135	29
40	135	23
50	130	16
60	130	10
70	110	12
85	090	12
100	070	6
MAX	MIL	
TROP	193	-67
	145	25
10	1621	
15	1366	
20	1189	
25	1031	
30	935	
40	740	
50	580	
70	322	
85	166	
100	35	
10	253.0	
15	177.0	
20	130.0	
25	116.0	
30	105.0	
40	160.0	
50	258.5	
70	286.5	
85	131.3	
100	545.0	
10	-59	
15	-59	
20	-66	

**BOULMER
03240
AT 11Z**

10	305	14
15	315	19
20	030	13
25	280	4
30	135	3
40	345	12
50	335	16
60	345	18
70	360	16
85	015	13
100		
MAX	MIL	
TROP	182	-72
	085	3
10	1614	
15	1361	
20	1188	
25	1051	
30	935	
40	739	
50	579	
70	321	
85	165	
100	34	
10	253.0	
15	173.0	
20	137.0	
25	116.0	
30	104.0	
40	161.0	
50	257.5	
70	286.7	
85	130.6	
100	543.0	
10	-59	
15	-61	
20	-69	

**LONG KESH
03920
AT 11Z**

10	265	12
15	290	11
20	135	20
25	165	12
30	195	9
40	200	12
50	175	10
60	170	3
70	115	9
85	025	6
100		
MAX	MIL	
TROP	200	-69
	135	28
10	1617	
15	1363	
20	1189	
25	1052	
30	936	
40	741	
50	580	
70	322	
85	166	
100	36	
10	254.0	
15	174.0	
20	137.0	
25	116.0	
30	105.0	
40	161.0	
50	258.4	
70	286.1	
85	130.7	
100	544.3	
10	-59	
15	-61	
20	-69	

FACIT 4-UP
28 JAN '97 13:44

12Z 28 JAN 1997

500-1000MB
500MB

THICKNESS DM.
HEIGHT DM.

GMATN I+ 0

VT 00Z TUES 28/ 1/97

01 00Z TUES 28/ 1/97

01 00Z TUES 28/ 1/97

PHEA50 EGRR 0000Z

CHART 13

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03:45:02

01 00Z TUES 28 / 1/97 VI 00Z MED 29 / 1/97 GMAIN 1 + 24 - - - THICKNESS DM. 500-1000MB HEIGHT DM. 500MB

28 JAN 97 04:06

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_5 PAGE. 001

01 HR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.45.13 CHART 13 PHEE50 EGR 0000Z

BAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03:30:55

CHART 27

PHDA30 EGRR 0000Z

PHDE30 EGRR 0000Z

CHART 27

AF: STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.38.39

H967

SNOW PROBABILITY AT MSI
TOTAL PPN RATE
PRESSURE AT MSI

TOTAL ACCUMULATION
50MB NET BULB POT TEMP 01 12Z TUESDAY 28/1/1997 LMRN

RAINFALL IN MM DURING THE 6 HOURS ENDING AT VT

28 JAN '97 14:35

Meteosat-IR 280197 1500GMT

Level 2 28/01/97

From 15Z 26/ 1/1997 to 18Z 28/ 1/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

Level 3 28/01/97

From 15Z 26/ 1/1997 to 18Z 28/ 1/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

Level 5 28/01/97

From 15Z 26/ 1/1997 to 18Z 28/ 1/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

TDTRAJ_A5970128.TXT

From 15Z 26/ 1/1997 to 18Z 28/ 1/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

